

A Global Systems Science Approach for Urban Health and Wellbeing

Rethinking Health and Wellbeing in an Urbanising
World within Planetary Boundaries

Science plan and framework for action

2024

How to read this document

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“Cities have the capability of providing something for everybody, only because, and only when, they are created by everybody”

Jane Jacobs, 1961. *The Death and Life of Great American Cities*

“I think the next century will be the century of complexity”

Interview with San Jose Mercury News, Stephen Hawking, Jan 2000.

“The wrong view of science betrays itself in the craving to be right; for it is not his possession of knowledge, of irrefutable truth, that makes the man of science, but his persistent and recklessly critical quest for truth.”

The Logic of Scientific Discovery, Karl Popper, 1992.

“In a world now dominated by communications and in a world where most people will be living in cities by the end of this century, it is high time we changed our focus from locations to interactions, from thinking of cities simply as idealized morphologies to thinking of them as patterns of communication, interaction, trade, and exchange; in short, to thinking of them as networks.”

The New Science of Cities, Batty, 2013

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Executive summary

Cities have the potential to be beacons for global sustainable development – but only if they are healthy. They are places of innovation and creativity where people can create the circumstances needed to adjust to global changes and achieve the UN Sustainable Development Goals. Approaching sustainability from a systems science perspective to urban health and wellbeing can tie the social, economic and ecological pillars of sustainable development together. Further, it can solve the core sustainability dilemma of health and wellbeing being systemically linked but often mutually counteracting, so that human health achievements are not made at the expense of declining planetary health.

Despite numerous encouraging examples, many of the opportunities for urban health and wellbeing are still being foregone because organizational and institutional complexity of the past has not readjusted and kept pace with the requirements of current global and environmental changes in the Anthropocene epoch – the age in which humans are changing the planet and will leave traces of that change in geological time periods to come. Urban progress of the past cannot simply be projected into the future as business as usual. Decoupling strategies by improving efficiency of resource use and decreasing waste and pollution need to be complemented with recoupling strategies which match capacities with challenges and make new linkages for much needed collective and systems intelligence. Data collection systems need to be recoupled with new collaborative knowledge production systems to respond to the kind of complexity problem urban health and wellbeing is.

Monitoring, accounting and governance mechanisms are often not in place or not functioning as an integrated system to restore a healthy balance between people's needs, the planet's ecological capacity and the city's potential to play a balancing role for achieving an overall one urban health, which is a precondition for sustainable development.

This plan is the result of lessons learnt from 10 years of the International Science Council's global science programme on "Urban Health and Wellbeing: a Systems Approach". It makes a new case for a global systems science approach to Urban Health and Wellbeing and identifies and addresses the above-mentioned dilemmas and shortcomings.

The main target audience of this science plan are stakeholders in cities and scientists. The plan is written for cities that are seeking ways to collaborate with scientists in ways to unlock the potentials of people, nature and technology, especially in their systemic combination, to improve health and wellbeing within planetary boundaries, guided by the five goals: 1) Promote health in all Policies, 2) Establishing Data-Knowledge-Action systems for urban health and wellbeing, 3) Communicating the systems science approach, 4) Developing training and education material, 5) Building collective intelligence.

This plan deviates from the previous plan in that systems science for urban health and wellbeing is not only about the health and wellbeing of people living in cities and how multiple determinants of health interact in complex systems in service of people's health; nor is it merely about healthy cities. This plan moves cities into the center of a scientific enquiry, which needs to be '[post-normal](#)' and aims at a better understanding of cities as complex social, ecological and technological systems. It asks the questions of how health and wellbeing for

people in cities can be achieved without overstraining the functions and service of cities, or compromising planetary health. Further, it makes the case for a process of knowledge co-creation in cities, for cities, for and with people and the planet.

The overarching goal is, by means of a systems science approach, to enhance cities' capabilities and capacities so that new opportunities for urban health and wellbeing can emerge.

Principles, priorities and more specific goals have been defined which together shape this framework for a systems science approach to urban health and wellbeing. The programme provides a set of goals and aims at creating communities of practice in cities, where scientists, policy makers and urban residents co-create the urban environments in which urban health and wellbeing can emerge for sustainable development. Depending on specific action situations, actors, who are affected by and have a stake in making decisions, are part of new governance arrangements, which combine knowledge generation, decision-making and action-taking.

Systems thinking has been a core component of the programme since its [first science plan from 2011](#). It has led to new collaborations between health and urban science communities, to developing new partnerships, and new conceptual and analytical frameworks which are less deterministic and less anthropocentric, and shifted the focus of analysing from the determinants of human health in cities to the interconnections between human, urban and planetary health and eventually led to rethinking the quality of life and urban futures which can, e.g., be mapped on a broad spectrum between [Society 5.0](#) and [Ecological Civilization](#).

In sum and looking ahead, this science plan is innovative and implementation-effective and focuses on the following aspects:

- Health and urban scientists (incl. social scientists) need to work together better and closer to generate a common understanding of the kind of problem health and wellbeing in cities is, the lessons learnt from systems science and the knowledge shared between the health and urban sciences.
- Definitions, concepts and frameworks of urban health and wellbeing need to shift from being exclusively human-centered to being more urban centered, recognizing the city as a complex social, ecological and technological system.
- The concepts of health and wellbeing have entered important global political agreements and agendas, like the [New Urban Agenda](#), the [Paris Agreement](#) or the [UN Sustainable Development Goals](#). A global science programme in collaboration with UN agencies, like UN Habitat, and other organisations can play an important role in localizing global goals and agendas and facilitating knowledge co-creation.
- Cities have the largest environmental impact on earth, but also the greatest opportunities to respond to them. Achieving health and wellbeing goals in urban environments has numerous co-benefits and is thereby a more tangible goal on the way to achieving the Global Sustainability Goals, than trying to reach them individually.
- Cities should have permanent establishments for integrated knowledge co-production in response to urban health and wellbeing challenges. These could be centers for urban health and wellbeing, where transdisciplinary knowledge is constantly

produced, deliberated, updated, and effectively used for learning, decision making and action. The global science community should support cities in establishing science centers for urban health and wellbeing and collaborate in running them.

- Cities should invest in exchanging knowledge with scientists and urban residents, including politicians and private sector actors, on complex issues of urban health and wellbeing. Holistic urban health checks should be routinely carried out.
- Cities should take the lead in generating knowledge commons for urban health and wellbeing, in science and society, by providing funding for and implementing actual projects. In return, cities should receive financial incentives to attract talent and create optimistic investment climates for innovators.
- Cities should also lead in creating alliances with partner and sister cities and companies on the cross-cutting issue of health and wellbeing, to enable mutual learning globally and to demonstrate what cities can achieve by building collective intelligence.
- Before an effective architecture for earth system governance can be established, urban systems governance for health and wellbeing would be a more realistic and achievable intermediate step. Long-term commitment and political responsibility are prerequisites for such urban systems governance.
- The strategy to achieve such urban systems governance for health and wellbeing needs to be one of contextualizing and prioritizing the global goals using local and experiential knowledge to address context specific challenges. There are no panacea for making the best choices and at the same time there is an urgent need to transform. That means cities are often faced with a paradox of choice.
- A politics of uncertainty and unpredictability and making choices that are good enough and allow for making new decisions based on accelerated learning cycles could, in many cases, be an important step towards reaching the common sustainability goals.

PART 1 – Background

1.1 The changing global context and the need for a systems science approach to Urban Health and Wellbeing

In September 2011 the International Science Council's (then ICSU) General Assembly approved the establishment of the **Urban Health and Wellbeing: a Systems Approach** global science programme and in October 2014 the programme was launched and its secretariat was inaugurated at the Institute of Urban Environment, Chinese Academy of Sciences, in Xiamen.

Since then, the global science context changed and the focus of attention for urban health has shifted in two ways, both which shifted the traditional health sciences towards a new domain described as the new urban health science¹:

- 1) The unit of analysis has shifted from being less anthropocentric to more urban- and ecocentric. Urban health is less understood as the health of people living in cities and more so, as the health of cities and the health of their environments on which it depends.
- 2) The systems approach is not only applied to understand the interrelations between multiple determinants of human health in cities, but also the behavior and healthy functioning of complex urban social-, ecological-, and technological systems.

In order to understand how we have come to this stage; it is also important to understand the changing global science context and how it plays out in cities of countries in very different development conditions. The aim of creating health and wellbeing in cities happens in the context of the sustainable development goals but also in the context of increasing complexity.

When Stephen Hawking, in 2000 responded to a question about the way that science is developing, he replied: "I think the next century will be the century of complexity" and he was pointing towards the emerging field of complexity science that aimed at finding order in highly interconnected, complex systems such as the city, traffic movement, or ecosystems. Since then, what has become known as 'Complexity Theory' is finding application in many areas, from global financial systems, social network theory to the workings of the brain.

Current new global science development paradigms are perceived within the ecological and resource boundaries of the earth. The preconditions of development have changed: in the past the world was full of nature but relatively void of people, artifacts and waste they produce. That was the 'empty world'.² Today, in a 'full world', the satisfaction of needs and wants is more constrained by the availability of resources and the ecological services provided by the biosphere and its ecosystems (Figure 1). Although in the past technological advancements have repeatedly enabled humans to escape the Malthusian trap, they may have eventually reached the limits to growth^{3,4}.

In that new global context, two major development trajectories for industrial and for developing countries have been suggested. Both shall not have the right to appropriate global resources disproportionately. Each country would need to endeavor to achieve the common

goal of resource consumption without compromising the demands of other countries, while at the same time remaining within the carrying capacity of the biosphere. This model of development has been referred to as “contraction and convergence”.⁵

“Full”, big world on a small planet

“Empty”, small world on a big planet

Figure 1: The changing global development context: From a small world on a big planet to a big world on a small planet. Changes of tectonic dimensions happen as the pressure of a bigger world on the planet's ecosystems and biodiversity increases and socio-ecological interconnectedness, complexity and systemic risks increase (Author's illustration and adapted from [UNDRR, 2022](#) and [Daly, 2015⁶](#)).

Similar to the idea of safe and just earth system boundaries⁷, the model combines ecology and justice and assumes ecological and resource limits. It requires that the industrial countries contract by reducing their consumption of resources, and developing countries can increase their resource consumption to an upper limit of ecological sustainability. That could be achieved through a combination of efficiency, consistency and sufficiency, or a combination of green growth and degrowth⁸.

Contraction and convergence require a combined strategy of efficiency, consistency and sufficiency.⁹ The idea of **efficient** resource consumption is to reduce the use of materials and energy per unit of goods and services, through improved technology and organisation, recycling and waste avoidance.¹⁰ For **consistency**, the challenge is that technology needs to be compatible with the environment. Industrial metabolic processes should mimic natural cycles, complement, or even reinforce each other, like in circular economy and industrial ecology approaches. In both, natural cycles are mimicked and closed-loop systems promoted. Materials are kept in circulation for as long as possible, e.g., through recycling and composting, and products are designed to be durable and repairable. **Sufficiency** is about the question of how much is enough; how not to fall into excess and overconsumption, but to use only as much as is beneficial for the health and well-being of people and the planet.

The changing global development context opens new opportunity spaces (Figure 2) which can emerge when complexity and socio-ecological interconnectivity increase. Such opportunity spaces are created when, e.g. people collaborate in managing the urban commons, or when new employment opportunities in the digital economy are created. Filling emerging opportunity spaces requires investments in building trust, communication and building social capital, also to reduce risks from increasing systemic complexity. Filling the opportunity spaces of increasing complexity requires fundamental shifts from individual to social types of rationality and from instrumental to communicative type of human interaction.

On the other hand, mismatches and lacking fit between institutional arrangements and the nature of the complexity problem which requires a particular type and structure of rules and institutional design, explain governance failure and foregone opportunities^{11,12}.

Along the same lines, members of the Urban Health and Wellbeing programme have proposed a framework of thinking about future health and wellbeing from a complex systems perspective¹³, which draws on Tainter's¹⁴ theory of why complex societies collapse. His interpretation of the cause of the collapse is that in the course of development, social problem-solving becomes more complex and costly, i.e. social institutions become increasingly differentiated, integrated and interconnected. In the initial stages of development social complexity increases due to increasing marginal returns from complexity. In later stages of development marginal returns diminish or generate negative returns. Innovation becomes more costly and reaches diminishing returns. This declining trend is enhanced when, e.g., new limits to growth are defined by setting planetary boundaries and by a reduced capacity of ecosystems to absorb waste and pollution (Figure 3).

Figure 2: Opportunity spaces of increasing complexity can be filled by shifting towards social rationality and communicative styles of human interaction (Source: Adjusted from Vatn 2005¹⁵ illustrated in UNDRR GAR 2022¹⁶)

To maintain or increase returns from complexity, increasing frequencies of innovations or energy subsidies are required. [West](#) who investigates scaling laws in cities, in his book “[Scale](#)” (2017)¹⁷, explains the situation of diminishing returns to complexity as follows: “We’re not only living on an accelerating treadmill that’s always getting faster and faster, but at some stage we have to jump onto another treadmill that is accelerating even faster, and sooner or later have to jump from that one onto yet another one that’s going even faster. And this entire process has to be continually repeated into the future at a faster and faster rate. (...) a bizarre psychotic behavior (which cannot) be sustained without our having a collective heart attack”.

Since the [great acceleration](#) around 1950, despite the warnings of reports like ‘[Our Common Future \(1987\)](#)’, and ‘[Limits to Growth \(1972\)](#)’, or the UN Conference on Environment and Development in [Rio 1992](#), the world has further transformed into [a big world on a small planet](#) which is crossing [planetary boundaries](#) only within which sustainable and peaceful development is possible. Also, the world has become less compartmentalised and more interconnected, which enhances the interlocking crisis, i.e., an environmental crisis which is linked to an energy crisis, which is linked to a economic development crisis.

Figure 3: Initially increasing, later diminishing marginal returns from (urban) complexity. Point B1/C1 represents the point where a technical innovation or new energy subsidy is adopted. This will often have the potential, at least temporarily, to raise marginal productivity (Source: Adapted from [Tainter 1988](#))

In such a context, where boundaries are crossed, tipping points are reached and risks of cascading effects increase, the UN secretary General in September 2021, projected two scenarios: [breakdown or breakthrough](#). Breakdown will be the default consequence should we choose a 'business as usual' strategy and resist [transformational change](#). 'Breakthrough' and innovation can be achieved by energy subsidies, technology innovations or unlocking the human resource of social capital and [collective intelligence](#).

The question now is: which consequences does this new global development context have for a global science programme on systems science for urban health and wellbeing? A new phase of the global science programme on urban health and wellbeing needs to create a better understanding of where cities are positioned on the aforementioned complexity development trajectory. The opportunity spaces which open for cities to achieve the sustainability goals, depend on their initial conditions. Despite the absence of perfect knowledge of these initial conditions and the behaviour of the urban systems, systems science can provide the epistemological and ontological framework and open a toolbox of methods for cities to better cope with complexity. Equipped with those tools, cities can make decisions which are appropriate responses to the health and wellbeing challenges cities are confronted with.

A systems science approach to urban health and wellbeing needs to go beyond crossing disciplinary boundaries; it needs to speak to citizens and decision makers at all levels - not only aim at extracting data from people, and involve them in a knowledge co-creation, learning and co-governance process. This is where science in action becomes interdisciplinary, transdisciplinary¹⁸ and participatory. Due to the changing global context and the accelerated learning required to keep up with global change challenges, knowledge production, communication of knowledge and eventually knowledge implementation can no longer happen in separate domains waiting to be reconnected. They need to happen as part of one concerted and integrated science-governance process, here referred to as the [Data-Knowledge-Action system](#).

Data, knowledge and action domains need to merge and be combined into data-knowledge-action systems, which are systems of social learning, where citizens and other stakeholders become active co-creators of knowledge and scientists facilitate the process. By engaging in such knowledge co-production process, communities themselves become the model for solving their own sustainability challenges, instead of outsourcing knowledge production and modelling to external scientists and experts.

Urban development with a focus on a systems science approach to health and wellbeing has the potential to reconcile the economic, social and environmental dimensions of sustainable development and bring development back to an operating mode which is ecologically safe, economically thriving, and socially just.

With such an understanding of the global development context future cities need to be seen on a complexity trajectory (Figure 3). Depending on their specific current position, future cities and city regions are likely to become more complex and attempts to improve health and wellbeing, more challenging.

As we have entered the Anthropocene epoch, the planet has become predominantly urban and cities need to transform from the Holocene to the low-entropy Anthropocene city to create healthy urban environments and wellbeing for its residents (Figure 4).

Parasitic cities¹⁹ have an ecological footprint that degrades the very environment they depend on and have no intention or mechanism in place to reduce their ecological footprint and thereby improve their urban health status.²⁰ The energy and resource needs of parasitic cities are predominantly met from outside their boundaries and they have little or no intention to reduce their ecological footprint and become more energy and resource self-sufficient, e.g. by urban agriculture. This definition of parasitic cities is consistent with the definition of [human intelligence](#), which requires adaption and intentionality. Parasitic cities then show no or low levels of intention to improve their resource and energy efficiency.

Symbiotic cities, are more [intelligent](#) than that. They aim at achieving a salutogenic health balance of people, cities and the planet. Both, parasitic and symbiotic cities are, to a certain degree, low entropy cities. Both depend on resources and energy from outside their boundaries and cannot achieve full self-sufficiency. The difference is that symbiotic cities have (social) mechanisms in place which aim at improving their resource use efficiency.

Another distinction is that between high and low entropy cities. “A low entropy city is defined as a responsive and conscious autopoietic human sociocultural niche that evolves and grows, enhancing its socio-ecological and structural complexity (reducing internal entropy) by adding and optimizing functional elements and synapses among those elements, while wastes (exported entropy to the biosphere) are minimized.” (Pelorosso et al. 2017).

In the context of earth system boundaries, new urban boundaries (e.g., for resource and energy consumption) must also be defined. That will lead to new urban designs, urban forms and functions, like the anti-fragile, spontaneous, fractal or the networked city, cities which prioritize the human scale of a healthy urban life with the aim of not deteriorating the health of the environment on which it ultimately depends.

Figure 4: Low entropy cities reduce externalities by creating value in additional social, economic and ecological opportunity spaces, thereby improving human, urban and environmental health. Precondition for the shift from high to low entropy cities are innovations or energy subsidies. (Source: Pelorosso et al. 2017, Artwork by Dall-e)²¹

1.2 Lessons learnt

The previous science plan of the Urban Health and Wellbeing: a Systems Approach programme promoted the use of systems thinking and systems methods for the study of urban health and wellbeing. In particular it aimed at a better understanding of the interactions and interdependencies of social and environmental determinants of human health and thereby promoted a methods-driven approach to urban health and wellbeing.

This new science plan extends epistemological and ontological domains (Figure 15) and places it into a new, [post-normal](#) and transdisciplinary science context, which aims to respond to knowledge needs of decision makers at all levels in a rapidly changing uncertain world, in which values are in dispute, and decisions are urgent. In such circumstances it has become paramount to base a systems science programme on urban health and wellbeing not only on an approach which favours systems methods but one which is based on the science of cities as complex (adaptive) systems. A better understanding of cities as complex systems is essential for understanding urban health and wellbeing and vice versa.

Complexity science of cities has come of age and therefore the time has come for a **systems science programme for urban health and wellbeing**. Authors from different regions of the world have each elaborated why and how a systems approach to urban health and wellbeing has come of age in [China](#), in the [Aisa-Pacific Region](#), in [Africa](#), in [Latin American and the Caribbean](#), in [Latin American Cities](#), and in [ASEAN](#).

Two other key lessons from complexity science for urban health and wellbeing²² have been learnt in the first decade of the Urban Health and Wellbeing (UHWB) programme, which have practical and implementation relevance:

Firstly, building data-knowledge-action systems for urban health and wellbeing: A global science programme can advance the understanding of cities as complex systems and enhance cities' capacity to cope with that complexity. The ability to recognise cities as systems of subsystems and determine the systemic state of a city or urban community, can help determine in which sectors a city needs to invest and embark on a specific contraction or convergence strategy for sustainable development.

Secondly, a global science programme that is taking a systems science approach to urban health and wellbeing can facilitate and accompany the building of urban capacities for assessing a city's complex urban health condition, identify interventions for action and formulate policies in response to a city's specific development stage which is closely associated with its complexity condition. This is about building capacity to measure, monitor, model and manage a city's urban health and wellbeing condition. The programme has developed and tested a collaborative modelling tool to do so and provided evidence for the usefulness of such an approach, e.g., in the city of Beirut, Lebanon²³ and Guangzhou, China.²⁴

As mentioned in the previous section, the global development context plays out very differently for cities in different countries and which are in different stages of development. Cities in countries whose BIP is based on agriculture, in countries that are industrialized or countries that generate the majority of their wealth from the service sector, are on very

different trajectories of growth and development and therefore they are likely to prioritize very different strategies towards urban health and wellbeing. While some cities will focus on basic infrastructure and service delivery or the transformation of service delivery infrastructures, others will focus more on improving their governance performance, advance digitalization, or both.

The purpose of this science plan is to consolidate, exchange and further develop knowledge on a systems science approach to urban health and wellbeing. It aims at providing the context, guidelines, principles and methods for cities to take their own systems science informed approaches towards improving urban health and wellbeing.

So far, the programme has done so by creating knowledge, networks, facilitating the exchange of knowledge, developing and testing methods, as well as identifying and publishing evidence and best practice. The COVID-19 pandemic was an important opportunity for cities to learn from another and learn about the advantages of taking a systems approach to urban health and wellbeing²⁵.

Further efforts are needed to communicate and exchange ideas between disciplinary fields and especially facilitate more dialogue between the science and the policy communities in cities, especially by reaching out and establishing closer links to urban communities, municipalities and mayor networks and thereby strengthening science-policy dialogue and collaboration.

This science plan aims at providing a framework for all cities that decide to improve their [systems intelligence](#) for urban health and wellbeing, by taking a systems approach to urban health and wellbeing to implement global goals such as the New Urban Agenda and the Sustainable Development Goals at the urban, municipal, district and neighbourhood levels. For that to happen, urban governance, i.e. decision making in the city, needs to be adjusted by adopting or improving systems which are inclusive (of all stakeholders of an urban health [action situation](#)), integrative, and intelligent. In the following we will refer to such systems as [Data-Knowledge-Action systems](#).

Adopting the framework has the potential to improve a city's systems intelligence and its capacity to cope with health-related urban complexity challenges in a fast-changing global development context. Thereby cities can improve their health and wellbeing self-assessment, measuring and monitoring capabilities and identify policies which improve the health and wellbeing of its inhabitants and achieve two goals with one systems approach: improving urban health and wellbeing and reducing the urban impact on planetary health.

This science plan builds on insights which have been generated by members of the programme since the first science plan for the Urban Health and Wellbeing Programme was published in 2011²⁶. It builds on a set of critical publications that have been elaborated in the first decade of the programme and underpin this new science plan:

- ◇ The [Xiamen Call for Action](#) outlining universal principles of urban health
- ◇ The [Interdisciplinary Science-Action Plan 2021-2025](#)
- ◇ The [UNDRR GAR 2022 "Our World at Risk"](#) (relevant for urban health governance)

- ◇ The commentary on [Towards a New Urban Health Science](#)
- ◇ The [Urban Health and Wellbeing Policy Brief series volumes 1-3](#)

This new science plan puts science for urban health and wellbeing on a new trajectory and firmly bases it on the foundations of the new urban sciences and their understanding of cities as complex systems. Complex systems science connects the understanding of how cities create wealth for their residents in the context of peri-urban and global environments and networks. Complex systems science should be further explored to better understand how urban ecosystems can be built in a more symbiotic relationship with other social and ecological systems of the earth.

This new science plan deviates from the original plan from 2011 in that it emphasizes the fundamental dilemma and conflict between peoples' health and wellbeing and urban and planetary health: Healthy cities can function in ways to improve the health and wellbeing of people by providing access to goods, services and opportunities. Creating that urban advantage in the process of urban development has, however, also largely contributed to the crossing of planetary boundaries or reaching the limits of safe earth system operating spaces which, in turn, compromises planetary health and the health and wellbeing of people living in cities. Addressing this [systemic dilemma](#) (

Figure 5) between people's health in cities and planetary health, the social and ecological determinants of health need to be considered ^{27,28}.

Figure 5: Addressing the dilemma of improving human health and wellbeing for more people living in cities which require more energy without compromising planetary health.

Lessons learnt from Cities under COVID-19

Wernli et al. (2021)²⁹ underline the importance of a multi-systemic resilience approach to a health pandemic, such as COVID-19 and [Howden-Chapman et al. \(2023\)](#) could draw important lessons for urban health and wellbeing from how COVID-19 (2019-2022) played out in different cities around the world:

1. Cities are in need of a whole-of-society approach for action.
2. Legitimate state actors need the freedom to develop strategic short- and longer-term policies and fund an enact appropriate public health measures
3. Multi-level governance for pandemic emergency response is compromised, e.g. by military of political intransigence.
4. Different layers of government need well developed communication structures.
5. Willingness to learn from other cities' successful responses, domestically and internationally.
6. Intra-city mutual support of neighbors and neighborhoods.
7. Protect the systems of accountability and freedom of speech for public health.
8. Through transparent communication avoid decline of trust towards public health authorities and counterbalance the spread of deliberate misinformation.
9. Quick fixes, such as lockdowns, alone are inadequate and more sophisticated measures are need in the medium term.
10. Command and control approaches can compromise human rights and worsen public trust.
11. Social cohesion and broad conformity with strict disease prevention policies
12. Gaining and maintaining the cooperation of the population requires communicating, building collective awareness and trust and creating a society where governments and community organisations work together closely.

The overarching goal of the systems science programme on Urban Health and Wellbeing, responds to all those lessons learnt during COVID-19. The goal is to create systems intelligence for a better understanding of the complexities of urban environments in which opportunities for and from urban health and wellbeing can emerge. That systems intelligence can be built long before a pandemic hits a country, thereby making it better prepared to respond.

There is no universally agreed concept of health system governance. During the COVID pandemic, new adaptive approaches to governance had surfaced, where civil society groups, religious organizations, private companies, nongovernmental organizations provided support to governments.

Greer et al.³⁰ suggest five criteria which are useful for assessing the quality of health system governance – not only during a pandemic:

- 1) Transparency – revealing, explaining and communicating the rationale of decisions made and by whom
- 2) Accountability – being accountable for the decisions made
- 3) Participation – including and listening to those who are affected by the decisions made
- 4) Integrity – a decision-making system where organisations and procedures are consistent and clear to facilitate seamless coordination.
- 5) Capacity – decisions are made on the basis of knowledge and expertise.

Political economists assume that global challenges, such as pandemics and climate change, require global or multi-national solutions. Many of these challenges are addressed at the micro-level before enforceable international agreements have been made.³¹

Polycentric governance for urban health and wellbeing seems to be a viable option (Figure 6). “Polycentric” connotes many centers of decision making that are formally independent of each other. . . . To the extent that they take each other into account in competitive relationships, enter into various contractual and cooperative undertakings or have recourse to central mechanisms to resolve conflicts, the various political jurisdictions in a metropolitan area may function in a coherent manner with consistent and predictable patterns of interacting behavior. To the extent that this is so, they may be said to function as a “system”. (Ostrom et al. 1961)³²

Polycentric governance could be found across the public health domain in the developing world. Mistree (2022)³³ reports that beginning March 2019, many of the states of South Asia quickly and forcefully ensured that they would control the governance response to the COVID-19 pandemic. Previously, powerful non-state entities were marginalized and this sudden transition affected how states have responded to the COVID-19 pandemic and is also likely to shape the governance of public health and infectious disease in future.

Figure 6: Polycentric governance for health and wellbeing. In the absence of a universally agreed health system governance, a pandemic-like health emergency does not need to be either fully controllable or self-regulatable.

1.3 Transformative shifts and innovative concepts

According to the [Human Development Report \(HDR\)](#), “Uncertain Times, Unsettled Lives: Shaping our Future in a Transforming World” 2021-2023 an “uncertainty complex” has emerged in our time, comprising of 3 volatile and interacting dynamics:

1. destabilizing planetary pressures and inequalities of the Anthropocene,
2. the pursuit of sweeping societal transformations to ease those pressures and
3. widespread and intensifying polarization.

For the first time in 32 years, the Human Development Index (HDI), which measures a nation’s health, education, and standard of living, has declined globally for two years in a row. 9/10 countries’ human development has declined, and human development has fallen back to its 2016 level, reversing 5 years of progress towards the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

This global science programme on Urban Health and Wellbeing aims at responding to that global uncertainty complex by applying a systems approach and a salutogenic conceptualization of urban health, which sees (healthy) cities in the position of negotiating human and planetary health. The principles and methods proposed, aim at enabling cities to better understand and respond to the human, urban and planetary health challenges - not only within urban system boundaries but recoupled to people (who move in and out of cities) and the planet.

It is important to understand some of the more specific transformative shifts the world is currently undergoing in order to adequately respond by changes in urban health and wellbeing. Those shifts shape the science and research landscape for urban health and wellbeing and explain the necessity of a systems science approach: in a bigger world on a smaller planet, human activities have ecological consequences (costs) which are no longer externalizable or absorbable for free. Increasing interconnectivity of social and ecological systems trigger feedback loops to society, e.g., in form of declining health from environmental pollution.

The challenge is now to find ways of avoiding and internalizing those costs. This requires innovations and behavioral changes. The opportunities also lie in increased interconnectivity: technology produces better and more data and enables better measurement, monitoring, and modelling of causes and consequences of the interactions between people and their environments.

Some of the transformative shifts and innovative concepts relevant for urban health and wellbeing are described in the following sections:

- Changing development paradigms
- Health is becoming a proxy for sustainable development
- Transforming uncertainties to opportunities
- From global to local (urban) commons
- From an anthropocentric to a holistic concept of health
- Methodological shifts for a systems approach to urban health and wellbeing

Changing development paradigms

Taking a systems approach to urban health and wellbeing marks a fundamental paradigm shift in thinking about the role and position of humans in the world.³⁴ Emmanuel Kant (1724-1804) triggered a paradigm shift in science and philosophy. In 'Critique of Pure Reason'³⁵, Kant fundamentally changed the relationship between the human actor and the outside 'world' by arguing that humans can not perceive reality as it is, instead human thought actively changes and constructs reality. That means, humans cannot perceive the world 'as it is', rather only in ways they can think about the world. And the way humans think about the world requires, both rational thought and empirical evidence. That marked a fundamental shift in understanding the world.

Similarly, urban health science today needs to undertake the transition from a human-centered worldview towards a systems perspective. Health is commonly understood as a condition solely attributed to the human actor and in cities the human actor is in the center of the urban system, with concentric circles of social and environmental determinants of health, as depicted in the [Dahlgren and Whitehead "Rainbow Model"](#) (Figure 7) or its modified version in the [2011 Science Plan of the Urban Health and Wellbeing Programme](#) (Figure 8). The resulting understanding of 'urban health' is the health of people in cities.

The Anthropocentric worldview and the impact it has had on the conceptualization of urban health science, as outlined in the [2011 science plan](#), has however, fundamentally changed today, especially since the [2015 Rockefeller-Lancet commission report on Safeguarding Human Health in the Anthropocene Epoch](#) and the relatively recent field of planetary health; but also in the context of planetary boundaries and "a big world and a small planet"³⁶ – a concept which goes back to [Herman Daly's 2015 economics for a full world](#) and his previous work from 1996 on *The Economics of Sustainable Development*³⁷.

Growth, development and complexity often go hand in hand and result from the attempt to solve problems. From a complexity science perspective, the shift in development paradigms happens when marginal benefits from increasing complexity start declining (Figure 3). At that point the costs of maintaining what has been achieved in the previous phase of development, overtake the benefits. Additional costs arise from internalizing external costs and by redefining what is of economic value – a societal process in response to tighter earth system boundaries. Society and the economy shift from functioning linearly to circularly.

Figure 9 gives an overview of which transformative shifts can occur and how they can be seen as being interconnected. Gatzweiler (2014)³⁸ provides an explanation of institutional change and economic value in the process of development, depending on initial conditions.

Figure 7: Human health at the center of multiple determinants of health. Source: Dahlgren G, Whitehead M. 1991³⁹

Figure 8: Human (social, physical, mental) health and wellbeing at the center of multiple determinants of health. Source: [ICSU, 2011](#)

Figure 9: Interconnections explaining transformative shifts from a 'small world – big planet' to a 'big world-small planet'. Source: Author's illustration

Health as a proxy for sustainable development

Health is maybe the best proxy for sustainability; for the following reasons:

1. It is built on a principle of balance and sufficiency and thereby aims at avoiding overshoot, uneconomic growth, waste and pollution.
2. It has the potential to resolve the inherent sustainability dilemma of wanting to leave nobody behind in the pursuit of living better lives, and the impact this necessarily has on energy and resource use, ecosystem integrity and their limited capacity to provide goods and services.
3. It is a fundamental asset and driver for sustainable development.
4. It is applicable to humans, other living beings and cities.

The health of their residents is maybe the most important asset cities have to achieve the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by unlocking the potentials of healthy urban environments and a healthy planet (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Protecting the environment, protects health and is the precondition for sustainable development. Source: [WHO Europe](#) on X

The impact of urban development on the economy, on human and on planetary health, is enormous^{40, 41, 42} :

- 80% of global GDP is generated in cities.
- 50% of global waste comes from cities.
- 40% of urban growth is in slums that lack safe water and sanitation.
- 91% of people in urban areas breathe polluted air.
- 75% of global greenhouse gas emissions are produced in cities.
- urban land consumption will add 1.2 million km² of new urban built-up area to the world by 2030.
- globally, 1.81 billion people (that is 1 in 4 people) live in high-risk flood zones. Exposure is especially high in urban areas that lie in river plains and coastlines in developing countries, where 89% of the world's flood-exposed people live.
- cities have ecological footprints that are orders of magnitude larger than their physical area, exerting heavy impacts also on distant peri-urban and rural ecosystems.
- cities will expand to cover an additional 290,000 km² of natural habitat by 2030, particularly in the tropical forests of Africa and Asia

Transformations towards urban sustainability for a systems science programme on urban health and wellbeing therefore need to consider emerging research and priorities in the urban and health domains, the respective sciences and the problem of urban governance types to improve access to health and medical services. Many of those issues are related to threats and risks that emerge in the context of the [Anthropocene](#).

Urban governments and local communities are under pressure to manage multiple interconnected threats simultaneously as they lead to complex social, economic and health consequences. Population growth, ecosystem decline, and climate change can coincide and lead to migration. Food systems need to be designed to improve health, reduce poverty, and conserve biodiversity and ecological life support systems. Specific governance approaches, technologies and policies are needed to reduce the risks or the harm produced by these threats.

[The Lancet Commission on 21st-Century Global Health Threats \(2022\)](#) has identified a range of health threats emerging from current global trends, many of which play out in cities and need to be addressed by a systems science programme on urban health and wellbeing:

- COVID-19
- climate change
- conflict
- rising antimicrobial resistance,
- increasing obesity,
- inverted population pyramids,
- eroding sexual and reproductive rights for women,
- food insecurity,
- fraying multilateralism.

These impacts of global, urban and demographic developments on health need to be understood as systemically linked in order to make decisions and formulate policies which can contribute to achieving the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals.

Urban decision makers are confronted with situations of increasing urgency, high value contestation and uncertainty. But cities still do not know enough about how (un)healthy their mode of operation is and which impact they have on peoples' and planetary health. The costs of unsystemic urban development and growth now threatens the achievements made in urban health and wellbeing globally: cities are facing increasing systemic risks and social cohesion and collective action, which are necessary to build the human capital stock capable of finding solutions, are increasingly under pressure.

Now, in the new context of the Anthropocene and newly defined earth system boundaries, cities need to become more systemic by connecting loose ends of urban development. Old problems need to be addressed, e.g., non-communicable diseases, pollution and waste from cities into the environment, and new opportunities need to be grasped, e.g. urban farming, urban green spaces, diversifying the energy mix, engaging people in decision-making and creating additional opportunities. Addressing old problems and creating new opportunities for urban and planetary health go hand in hand.

With that knowledge cities can open new opportunity spaces for the local implementation of the global sustainability goals. Cities are prime locations where human, social and technological capital is concentrated and where most innovation and creativity happen. Cities are therefore best placed to implement the six transformations which have been recommended by the **International Institute for Applied Systems Science**⁴³ to achieve Sustainable Development Goals:

1. Human capacity, well-being and health
2. Consumption and production toward sustainable and just economies
3. Decarbonization and universal energy access
4. Food and nutrition, biosphere and water
5. Urban and peri-urban areas and mobility
6. Global environmental and human commons including the digital revolution

To achieve those transformations towards sustainability, some cities are still lacking the infrastructure, institutions, and capabilities to acquire and make use of data and co-create knowledge to make decisions and carry out actions which do not compromise environmental health for people's wellbeing and thereby negatively feed back on the achievements made.

In order to operationalize systems approaches for urban health and wellbeing in the context of planetary boundaries, the Urban Health and Wellbeing (UHWB) programme has proposed data-knowledge-action systems. Data-knowledge-action systems (Figure 21) for urban health and wellbeing are systems which consolidate three components of social learning into one functional system by means of which urban decision making becomes faster, more cost efficient, better informed, accountable, participatory and adaptive.

Transforming uncertainties into opportunities

Solving urban health and wellbeing problems confronts stakeholders with uncertainties, limited data, time, and computational capacity. In such situations conventional notions of rational action, under the premise of perfect information, are inaccurate and will typically fail to deliver desired outcomes.

Rather, in such typically complex decision-making situations, ecological rationality, which accounts for context, and collaborative or social rationality, which seeks to progressively approach better answers through a process of co-discovery, should be favored (Figure 2).

In contrast to previously proposed data-driven, technocratic and control-based solutions, like the [Rio's Operations Center](#), which focuses on monitoring and control by relying heavily on technology, here, taking a systems approach to urban health and wellbeing means combining objective and subjective, rationalist, empiricist, heuristic and participatory approaches. The aim is not for scientists to produce models by, e.g., developing rule-based models which rely on big data and enormous computer processing power. Rather, scientists are mediators in a process of creating real life models and thereby transforming uncertainties into opportunities.

Rather, the aim is to embrace uncertainties by extending the conventional domain of science into society and create living models where people engage in a process of investigation, deliberation and collective intelligence building to solve the urban health and wellbeing problems in their cities in a continuous process of learning.⁴⁴

Critical systems thinking in Information and Communication Technology for Sustainability, e.g., requires a critical systems heuristics (CSH) approach. CSH recognizes the limits of computational approaches in urban decision making and balances the tension between facts and values, and the notions of how people think about human life should be organized. The CSH approach has, e.g. been demonstrated in Sidewalk Labs 'smart city' project in Toronto.⁴⁵

To facilitate that process the UHWB programme has proposed the building of [data-knowledge-action systems](#). It is a model that integrates participatory scientific enquiry and governance. The model embraces the uncertainty inherent in complex systems and engages urban decisionmakers at all levels, from citizens to mayors, depending on the problem addressed, thereby supporting a politics of uncertainty⁴⁶, rather than one of control and command.

“...Uncertainties should not be reduced to risk, framed as a zero-sum threat that is in need of taming, controlling and managing, lest innovation is somehow ‘held back’ (...).

In today’s complex, turbulent, interconnected, globalised world, uncertainty must be embraced as perhaps more central than ever.

We argue that opening up to uncertainty offers opportunity, diversity and a politics of hope. This in turn offers a more plural vision of progress, defined according to different standpoints, with multiple modernities at play.”

([Scoones and Stirling 2020: 2](#))

From global to local (urban) commons

Such third way to the science and governance of cities leads to robust governance approaches which we are familiar with for the governance of common pool resources. Commons governance is not trapped by “either market or state”⁴⁷ ruled approaches. There are additional institutional options for solving commons dilemmas, when stakeholders (who are holding a stake in the solution of a commons dilemma) can agree and commit themselves to a cooperative strategy that they themselves will put into practice.

The shifting global context from a ‘small world’ to a ‘big world’, the recently set earth system boundaries⁴⁸ new calls for limits to growth⁴⁹, and the continued pressure to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals, has led to calls of institutional and governance reforms to facilitate new global commons governance in the Anthropocene⁵⁰, new principles for global commons governance, and a revival of the idea of governing the urban commons.^{51,52}

Nakicenovic et al. (2016)⁵³ have suggested three principles for governing global commons which underly a proposed new social contract for planetary stewardship in the Anthropocene:

1. Inclusivity. The Global Commons in the Anthropocene are not external to human activity; they are internal to development at all scales and need to be treated inclusively.
2. Universality. Managing the Global Commons in the Anthropocene requires a paradigm shift in human worldviews toward planetary stewardship.
3. The Resilience. Planetary stewardship of the Global Commons in the Anthropocene is fundamentally about safeguarding social-ecological resilience, from local communities to Earth stability.

Despite the similarity of many local and global commons and although there is a clear shift towards perceiving global ecological life support systems and biomes as global commons, McGinnis and Ostrom (1995)⁵⁴ also expresses caution about the idea of simply upscaling from local to global commons governance: *“...The key problem in designing effective institutions to control adverse effects on the environment is matching the specific set of rules that are to be used with the attributes and dynamics of the physical, biological, and technological world of relevance in a particular cultural milieu. (...) The most important institutional changes for coping more effectively with political, economic, and environmental issues at the global level may be the development of open information and communication regimes to enhance the capabilities of actors at many levels to come to a better common understanding of both the physical as well as the economic and social aspects of global climate patterns.”*

The authors (ibid) themselves state that the idea that new principles and new worldviews are collectively adopted around the world for the global commons governance may be

“An urban commons represents shared material, immaterial or digital goods in an urban setting (...). It is beneficial for the individual and collective well-being, and the degradation of the urban commons is perceived as a loss.

It is built around the social issues of participation, collective action and self-organisation which are reflected through the term commoning: collectively creating, using and managing the commons (...).”

([Feinberg et al. 2021: 2](#))

utopian. Indeed, group homogeneity and the ability to communicate and agree on issues of common concern is a precondition for collective action. At a global level this homogeneity and collective group identity does not exist and new “systemic rivals”⁵⁵ have been declared. The US National Intelligence Council states that “the next 20 years of transition to a new system are fraught with risks. Strategic rivalries are most likely to revolve around trade, investments, and technological innovation and acquisition, but we cannot rule out a 19th century-like scenario of arms races, territorial expansion, and military rivalries.”⁵⁶

Cities are therefore more likely (than nations) to be in the position to localize the idea of governing the global commons in the Anthropocene. One example among numerous urban initiatives and networks is the urban initiative of the [doughnut economics action lab](#). The doughnut economics idea is to implement the planetary boundaries by defining two boundaries between which localized actions take place: the (upper) ecological ceiling and the (lower) social foundations boundaries. Localized action in the city can be governed by a mix of market, state or commons governance approaches. Both boundaries address the sustainable development goals of leaving no one behind and protecting the environment and the ecological life support systems of the earth (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Doughnut economics. Meeting the needs of all within the means of the planet. Economies operate within the (green) safe and just space, limited by ecological boundaries and social foundations. Source: <https://www.kateraworth.com/doughnut/>

From an anthropocentric to a holistic concept of health

What could be considered a Copernican revolution for urban health science, is the change in the relationship between the health of the human being (with its constitutional factors) and the social and environmental determinants of health. The attempt to improve human health and wellbeing in cities by changing and optimizing the urban (social, physical and ecological) environment for increasing numbers of people living in cities, can lead to detrimental human health effects when the health of the environment is compromised, e.g., by high-density living conditions and air/noise/light pollution. An exclusive anthropocentric worldview for health is therefore insufficient in the epoch of the Anthropocene and requires a shift towards a more holistic conception of health.

The changing relationship between human and environmental health requires a different understanding of what health actually is. Health is not only a systemic condition of humans, but also for other complex living systems, such as the environment and the city. In the Anthropocene it becomes evident that humans and their urban environments have to develop a symbiotic relationship for mutual health. Assuring human health by combating diseases (what is known as the pathogenetic approach) is a constant battle between humans and nature by trying to sustain human health at the expense of the health of other complex living systems. The pathogenetic approach gave rise to the rise of the pharmaceutical industry and led to a health dilemma: achieving health by merely combating disease is not sustainable. The pathogenetic approach leads to the dilemma that the foundations for health can be destroyed in the attempt to maintain (human) health.

Health, as defined in the constitution of the [World Health Organisation](#), is “a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity”. That concept of health, understood within the context of planetary boundaries needs to be adjusted for this systems science programme on urban health and wellbeing, to reflect the interdependence between human, urban and planetary health (Figure 12).

The definition of health used in this plan, builds on the salutogenic understanding of health. Health no longer only constitutes the human condition; health extends to the condition of the environment in which people live. Health is a state of constantly changing balance, a dynamic equilibrium that an individual has established within itself and to the social, natural and built environment.

The pathogenetic approach requires the use of external healing devices and interventions to eliminate the pathogenic factors – a battle against health risks and threats, which does not always guarantee human health due to the variability of predispositions. While recognizing its achievements, the approach can have negative consequences on the very environment presumed to be the origin of the health threats. That dilemma of the pathogenetic approach becomes evident, e.g., in the case of [antimicrobial resistance](#), cascading effects in health care⁵⁷, or health impacts from ecosystem alterations.⁵⁸

In contrast, the salutogenic approach considers health as a position on the health ease and disease continuum, it focuses on our understanding of the development and maintenance of health and on people’s “internal healing resources and potential for active adaptation to new

circumstances” to create health and wellbeing.⁵⁹ Aaron Antonovsky’s⁶⁰ salutogenic concept of health is profoundly more complex and asks what can lead to a healthy and meaningful life.

Figure 12: The salutogenic approach to urban health in the context of planetary boundaries is about the triple balancing challenge between population, urban and planetary health. Getting urban health right means to balance human and planetary health.

The salutogenic approach has found many applications in the urban health literature, by asking, how, through design, social organisation, urban planning and collaboration between multiple sectors human health in cities and towns can be achieved.^{61, 62, 63, 64}

The novelty of this approach applied to urban health science is that the city, not only the human actor, is perceived as a complex [living organism](#) and becomes the unit of analysis for scientific inquiry. This shift occurs together with the epochal transformation from the [Holocene to the Anthropocene](#), which is also a common assumption for the contemporary science on [earth systems boundaries](#). The challenge in this new era is to adjust human behavior and urban structure and functioning for human health and wellbeing within the limits of urban and planetary health.

Accordingly, **urban health** has been defined as the health of people living in cities and the complex state of the social, ecological and technological systems on which it depends.⁶⁵ It is important to note here that the ‘and’ implies people’s health in cities and the health of the urban and planetary systems, as being equally important aspects of urban health and that urban health should go beyond the multiple determinants of human health in cities. Human and [ecosystem health](#) overlap and interact in urban health (Figure 13).

Due to cities being defined as complex social, ecological and technological systems ([Bai et al. 2016](#)), urban ecosystem health needs be considered a more accurate terminology for what we mean with “urban health”. **Urban ecosystem health** refers to the linkages between social, ecological and technological systems in cities and their interactions with systems outside urban boundaries. Sometimes ecosystem health refers to the linkages between human activities, ecosystems and human health, but it also refers to the health of an ecosystem itself. This distinction, however, does not need to be made if we consider humans as integral part of urban ecosystems and do not restrict the concept of an ecosystem to the realm of the non-human. An urban ecosystem is healthy if it is robust and resilient and able to maintain its organization over time.⁶⁶ In order to be healthy, the urban ecosystem needs to maintain a homeostatic and symbiotic relationship with planetary health.⁶⁷

Figure 13: Urban health emerges from the interactions of complex social-, ecological-, and technological systems within urban system boundaries, that are embedded into and connected to earth system boundaries. Urban and planetary health are mutually dependent and determine human health.

In the context of the COVID pandemic which primarily played out in cities, urban health strongly overlaps with the of OneHealth approach. [OneHealth](#) is “an integrated, unifying approach that aims to sustainably balance and optimize the health of people, animals and ecosystems.” (Figure 14).

One Health underlines the interconnectedness of human, animal, and environmental health and becomes more relevant in the Anthropocene context, as increased travels, extreme weather events and emerging diseases have changed the interaction patterns in the biosphere, specifically between people, animals and plants. These interactions culminate and accelerate in cities and lead to health issues.

One Health has been promoted and recognized as a concept by the UN, the G20, and WHO.⁶⁸ Urban Health can be regarded as embodying a One Health strategy in cities. Cities are ideal test beds and locations for innovations in urban health. In “[Cities Under COVID 19: a Systems Perspective](#)” [Howden-Chapman et al. \(2023\)](#) provide insights into how cities in 15 countries, from India, Brazil, China to USA, New Zealand, Europe and Sub-Saharan Africa responded to COVID 19. It describes differences in how social actors responded to gaps in knowledge and to scientific uncertainty.

Figure 14: The OneHealth concept and the approach of the Lancet One Health commission (Source: Amuasi et al. 2020⁶⁹)

Methodological shifts for a systems approach to urban health and wellbeing

An important building block for the new science of urban health, is the integration of methodological approaches to understanding urban health as an emergent property of complex urban systems⁷⁰. Aaltonen and Sanders (2006)⁷¹ (Figure 15) have provided a useful framework which goes far beyond the proposed 'systems approach' in the first science plan from [ICSU 2011](#). It illustrates the ontological and epistemological assumptions made when applying different methods. The reality of urban systems, their complex relationship with urban populations and the emergent property of urban health is created and understood by choosing different methods of investigation.

The framework points to an essential insight which has been generated over the period of the UHWB programme's first decade: in the process of applying certain methods to understand what leads urban systems to produce desired health and wellbeing outcomes, urban health and wellbeing itself is created. The process becomes the product. The strict separation between (human) subject and object of investigation, as typical for [logical positivism](#), is overcome. In the investigative process, the methods applied are become knowledge inquiry in action and that process is part of a new [science-based governance for urban health and wellbeing](#).

Figure 15: A better understanding of complex systems depends on the choice of methods and their epistemological and ontological premisses. Data heavy and ambiguity removing methods are found in the bottom left quadrant, while participatory and ambiguity allowing approaches tend to be found in the top right quadrant. Source: [Aaltonen and Sanders \(2006\)](#)

A collaborative systems modelling tool has been proposed which require stakeholders to co-create the knowledge required to improve certain aspects of urban health and wellbeing in cities, e.g., [traffic noise reduction in a district of Beirut](#). In doing so the capacity of participating stakeholders to identify the problem and to co-create solutions is enhanced. Not only solutions to traffic noise reduction had been identified but also stakeholders' capacity to think and work together, which is an important urban health asset itself, a co-benefit of knowledge production for urban health and wellbeing.

The 2016 Gulangyu workshop April 28-29, on "[Modeling Urban Health and Wellbeing for policy and action: Algorithms vs Institutions](#)" came to the same conclusion that the urban health knowledge creation process itself (not just the outcome) is an important contribution to urban health and wellbeing. Practicing and being engaged in the knowledge co-creation and decision making for urban health and wellbeing, itself creates human and social capital and thereby improves urban health.

During that workshop participants discussed the role of models for a better systemic understanding of, and decision making on, urban health issues such as air pollution, infectious and lifestyle diseases (such as obesity and cardiovascular diseases); but also antibiotic resistance and the urban heat island effect, which exacerbates respiratory problems and causes heat stroke, exhaustion, and premature deaths. Rapid urban environmental change combined with climate change is not only a real threat to peoples' health and wellbeing but also their survival. Heat waves peak in cities and cause thousands of premature deaths every year. Just at the time of the meeting, a record heat wave hit India and South-East Asia.

Participants of that workshop concluded that modelling approaches for improving urban health and wellbeing, which merely collect data from stakeholders instead of also engaging them in the process of investigation and problem solving, can lead to very data heavy (agent based) models which produce outcomes which stakeholders no longer understand nor 'own'. While the outcomes of those models may be coherent with the data and algorithms which went into them, results are detached from stakeholder's solution seeking and problem-solving capabilities. The outcomes of such modelling approaches are useful for scientific insight and publications; however, their implementation remains highly improbable.

'Being and creating a (real-life) model for urban health and wellbeing' and 'modelling urban health and wellbeing' go hand in hand in outlining a framework for this science plan. While the latter approach creates the model for urban health and wellbeing by experts which generate knowledge from it and then attempt to communicate that knowledge to policy-makers, the former approach involves all stakeholders from the start and makes them part of the model.

The approach coincides with the idea that the city is not only a place that provides health services but a system which consists of multiple places and opportunities enabling healthy living. Along that line of thought, [principles for healthy sustainable places](#) have been formulated 2015 by the United Nations University International Institute for Global Health in collaboration with the Urban Health and Wellbeing programme.

The same concept of “[Healthy Urban Systems](#)” (instead of merely healthy people in cities) was adopted for designing a Massive Open Online Course at Lausanne University. The idea of ‘Being and creating a (real-life) model for urban health and wellbeing’ was also adopted by the government of El Salvador when, together with the Regional Office of the international Science Council and the Urban Health and Wellbeing programme, they implemented the [Modelo de Salud Urbana](#) (Urban Health Model). The model was an interministerial platform at national level where consolidated policy making across all sectors would take place, with the goal to modify the urban environment where people live, play and work to improve social, physical and mental health.

1.4 The new science of cities and urban health and wellbeing

There is a long history of understanding cities as complex systems.^{72, 73} In the mid-19th century, cities were conceptualized on the basis of observations of geometry, form. Half a century later, cities were perceived as evolving from networks and flows and more recently, cities are regarded as products of a combination of top-down planning and bottom-up, evolutionary, self-organizing processes.

Together with the emergence of complexity science the direction of systems theory changed from top down to bottom up. Cities were now regarded as open systems, more based on evolutionary processes of millions of individual and group decisions, rather than of grand design processes.⁷⁴

This change in approach can be explained, among others by the “the deep mismatch between theory and practice, problems and solutions, have led to a retreat from the certainty of science. (...) A view of planning that can easily accommodate changing value systems, the complexity of pluralism, and the notion of fallibility now seems much more appropriate. Thus the concept of planning as social learning and society-wide problem solving has become the accepted norm.” (Batty 2013).⁷⁵

This new approach speaks to the idea of [post-normal science](#).⁷⁶ Instead of only relying on a scientific process in the tradition of [logical positivism](#), decisions are made in informed processes of negotiation and deliberation. The planning and knowledge creation process now becomes one of social learning and collective rather than individual action.

In the new science of cities, urban complexity is understood as partly organized and partly as emergent. Therefore, cities are partly plannable and partly unpredictable and unplannable. Conceptualising cities as “integrated social networks imbedded in space and time” emphasizes the importance of models, where local structures are developed by planners with particular goals and information, but also see the city as “social reactor”.⁷⁷

This relates to a dilemma in planning which stems from the impossibility of having all information to meet the needs of all effected by an urban planning project. Due to the nature of complex urban systems some elements of the city can be planned while other self-organise and emerge.

One of the goals of a global science programme on systems science for urban health and wellbeing, should therefore be to promote an understanding of the new science of cities and the relevance it has for urban health and wellbeing.

Fundamental for a new science plan on systems science for urban health and wellbeing, is the new science of cities which recognizes cities as complex social-ecological-technological systems.⁷⁸ Health is now not only a systemic conditions of complex human organisms but also that of the city and the environment.

[Bai et al. \(2016\)](#) aim at defining and advancing a systems approach for sustainable cities and identify four key issues for the effective implementation of the SDGs and the *New Urban Agenda*:

- a) a radical redesign of the multilateral institutional setup on urban issues
- b) promoting regenerative culture, behaviour, and design
- c) exploring ways to finance a systems approach
- d) a new and enhanced role for science in sustainable development

Towards a Systems Science of Urban Health and Wellbeing

The shift in focus from a multiple determinants and systemic optimization perspective to one focusing on systemic interactions, implies a corresponding change in the structure of the urban health science. Whereas the ‘multiple determinants of health’ field can be studied by teams of researchers from multiple disciplines working in parallel, the latter requires consilience (converging evidence from many unrelated lines of inquiry) and the robust uptake of inter- and transdisciplinary inquiry. This, in turn, requires a greater focus on participatory processes in order to ensure the multiple lines of evidence needed to generate new insights and inform policy and practice (among other benefits).

In the words of Jane Jacobs, “Cities have the capability of providing something for everybody, only because, and only when, they are created by everybody.”⁷⁹

By its nature, a complexity-informed science of urban health would encourage a focus on the upstream root causes of urban health and environmental challenges, allowing for a more efficient, proactive approach rooted in prevention, rather than the more typical reactive mode that endeavors to alleviate problems. Through its embrace of inclusive participation and a focus on systemic unintended consequences, it would also offer insights and incentives for addressing pervasive social, institutional, and health inequities in cities⁸⁰.

In *Towards A New Urban Health Science*, [Gatzweiler et al \(2023\)](#) define four critical shifts to underpin a complexity-informed approach to urban health. These shifts have led to the development of **the data-knowledge-action model**, which is further elaborated under Goal 2 of this science plan. The critical shifts are about:

- 1) how we perceive the nature of the challenges we face (ontology) and our ability to have knowledge about them (epistemology);
- 2) the tools we use to derive that knowledge (methodology);
- 3) the way that we respond to and make decisions based on that knowledge (rationality);
and
- 4) the way we organize our institutions to promote such an approach (governance).

The transformational shift in urban health, from “the health of people in cities” to “the health of cities within their environments” has not fully taken on. Because cities are not universally understood as complex social, ecological and technological systems, and due to the financial and governance constraints cities are facing, urban governments have also not yet fully embraced the full potential of their city’s urban system functions. Table 1 gives an overview of urban system functions.

Better understanding how these urban systems functions are generated and how they interact has the potential to create addition opportunity spaces for employment and urban living. From an integrated systems perspective it is not only the green and blue areas of cities that provide goods and services.⁸¹ A systems perspective resulting in innovative designs of new urban infrastructure, promoting the integration of grey, green and blue infrastructure through institutional innovation and structural reorganization of data-knowledge-action systems have the potential of contributing to improved health and wellbeing, and greater resilience to climate change.

Table 1: Overview of urban system functions (Source: Gatzweiler et al. 2016)⁸²

Function	Description
Supporting	Benefits provided by physical space (habitat) and infrastructure for basic life support functions, e.g., waste management, water treatment and sanitation, and energy provision (electricity). Enabling flows of energy (captured in form of low entropy goods) and information. They are necessary for all other functions to be produced. Markets sometimes require physical space for exchange but market exchange can also take place in virtual spaces.
Provisioning	Benefits derived from the provision of manufactured goods and knowledge and the access to infrastructure for water, energy, food, transportation, social interaction, market exchange to maintain its population's health, internal structure, procedures and processes: e.g. (processed) food, (purified) drinking water, construction materials, machines, artifacts (e.g. furniture, bicycles), ICT devices, education and knowledge infrastructure (universities), hospitals.*
Regulating	Benefits derived from providing rules and regulation (institutional infrastructure) to keep the (bio-physical) infrastructure running: e.g., regulating access to social space, legal systems, education systems, markets. Means are laws, norms, cooperatives, law enforcement, disease and disaster management and emergency response systems, health service systems, environmental protection agencies.
Cultural	Benefits provided for humans in cities which are created in socio-cultural spaces. Social space and liberties for economic and political exchange, exchange of ideas, social exchange, recreation and leisure, space for spiritual enrichment, art and cognitive development. E.g. cultural events, "Heimat" (sense of belonging), exhibitions, libraries, cultural heritage values (e.g., historical places), cultural diversity.

Note: * In the provisioning category of urban system functions, universities and hospitals, for example, are listed as provisioning functions, providing the facilities for regulation functions to be provided, e.g. education and disease treatment. Knowledge institutions regulate the quality and quantity of knowledge provided to particular segments of society. The boundaries between providing and regulating functions are not always straightforward.

Urban health and wellbeing outcomes are the result of systems which function to produce goods and services which are of value to humans. The degree to which urban system functions deliver services for human health and wellbeing, very much depends on available forms of capital, institutions and governance capacities.

People in cities have started imagining and building new kinds of ecosystems and nature-based hybrid solutions that allow for a reconciliation between human development and functioning ecosystems. For addressing this challenge in cities Elmquist et al. (2019)⁸³ offer the following 5 principles:

1. Resilience management for healthy cities in the context of climate change must be based on a deep understanding of the complexity of urban systems and the functions they provide.
2. Climate change affects all urban system functions directly or indirectly, and thereby also human health and well-being. Urban green areas and greening of other types of infrastructure need to be planned and managed to respond to the increasing health risks of climate change in cities.
3. Nature-based solutions have been developed as an action response to increase resilience to environmental stresses and can be used to help reduce health risks of climate change in cities.
4. Managing resilience in urban systems requires adaptive and flexible governance styles on several scales in order to enhance multi-functionality of systems and functions that support urban health and well-being.
5. Our knowledge of urban system complexity and urban system functions needs to be translated into actions that are not only nature-based, but also governed by data-knowledge-action systems that recognize all urban inhabitants as stakeholders and enable collective learning for urban health under climate change.

New urban governance for health and wellbeing

Cities struggle to adapt to the challenges of the Anthropocene: Ageing populations, climate change, migration, security, globally interconnected economies, are only some of the challenges cities face as complexity increases in the process of urbanization. Governance for urban health and wellbeing is a challenge to cope with complexity. It includes all aspects of urban governance, not only those aspects relevant for human health in cities.

The question of how cities are governed, however, is far from being conclusively answered. Empirical evidence on the institutions and governance arrangements required in cities, which help them cope with social, ecological and technological complexities and work towards the sustainable development goals, is still lacking. To date, theories and academic studies on urban governance have not established a mature and consolidated field of study (Lucas, 2017).^{84,85}

Nevertheless, due to their agglomeration economies and the fact that cities are melting pots for culture and test beds for innovation, the expectations towards cities' capacity and competence to respond to global challenges, are enormous and often excessive (Parnell, 2016)⁸⁶.

Some authors have identified a trend in the way cities are run. The shifts from ‘government’ to ‘governance’, for example, or from ‘managerialism’ to ‘entrepreneurialism’.⁸⁷ That process is often understood as a relative decrease in power of local governments as compared to that of philanthropies, consultants, banks, business associations or civil society organizations.

The challenge of urban governance for health and wellbeing, is also related to the paradox of choice and decision making.⁸⁸ As complexity and abundances of possible choices increase alongside with information about each of the possible choices, making the best decisions does not become easier. That is due to the fact that information processing capabilities and decision-making costs increase, and decisions on how much information is sufficient to make decisions, need to be made. It is therefore important to identify the appropriate scale for urban governance, adopt a [politics of uncertainty](#) and define stop-rules which help deciding how much information is sufficient and which decisions are good enough. Further, good governance for urban health and wellbeing requires mechanisms that allow for improving mistakes and learning.

Governing urban complexity for health and wellbeing⁸⁹ is a challenge because it needs to deal with the tension of freedom versus organization⁹⁰, or laissez-faire and regulation. It is about governance at the edge of chaos – a transition space between order and disorder. Governance at the edge of chaos “requires the ability to maintain order to avoid loss in chaos and, at the same time, to be open to chaos in order to progress and avoid getting stuck.”⁹¹

The challenges cities are confronted with for transitioning towards sustainable development by politics of health and wellbeing, often do not match their institutional and financial capabilities. [daCruz et al \(2019\)](#) and Barber (2013)⁹², e.g., come to the conclusion that although the New Urban Agenda was negotiated and adopted by nation states, “effective moves towards empowering city or metropolitan governments to establish a transition to a more sustainable society are rare. Most countries both in the Global North and South do not seem to welcome these reforms.”⁹³ Europe, however, seems to be a fertile ground for multilevel governance and intergovernmental relations, where cities are often expected to be more self-reliant.

Transnational urban networks for knowledge and cultural exchange play an important role in tackling global sustainability challenges. Tavares (2016), e.g., identified 120 city networks globally, which seems to be evidence that subnational activism is growing much faster than that of states.⁹⁴

Goal 5 of this new science plan for urban health and wellbeing, therefore, calls for strong and active support from sponsors and supporters of the programme to connect the academic community to actors from outside academia that are most relevant for urban governance.

The Urban Governance Survey by LSE Cities, UN-Habitat, and UCLG (2016)⁹⁵ has shed some light on important urban governance issues and showed, e.g., that institutional mixes and multiscale relationships in urban governance are essential.

The level of mismatch between academic issues and actual governance concerns of cities, is another matter of concern in urban governance. Contemporary urban governance research shows a disconnection between academic and actual concerns of urban leaders and managers – a gap this science programme shall aim at addressing by the goals it is putting forward, especially Goals 1, 3, 4, and 5.

While the most studied urban governance challenges are:

- citizen participation
- engagement of civil society organizations with decision making and
- the lack of local governments' political engagement with the electorate,

the actual urban concerns, are:

- insufficient public budgets
- politicization of local issues
- the complexity of managing contemporary urban issues,
- maladapted or outdated policy silos
- overlapping responsibilities (unclear jurisdictions)
- vertical coordination issues (working across levels of governance)
- lack of municipal autonomy
- inflexible bureaucracies and rigid rules,

are significant challenges to effective urban governance.

For that reason, this new science plan of the Urban Health and Wellbeing programme aims at addressing those actual urban governance concerns, specifically through its systems thinking and collaborative modelling approach which is introduced under the second goal of this plan.

Inspired by evolutionary systems thinking a mixed method approach to urban governance and a structured so-called “urban tinkering”⁹⁶ process is proposed. This approach responds to urban governance issues when cities are understood as complex systems which are only partly plannable. Due to ambiguity avoidance⁹⁷, uncertainty triggers either rule-based or explorative and experimental governance approaches.⁹⁸

New urban governance solutions need to meet the technical possibilities of the day. The ubiquity of digital devices and the possibilities of big data, sensors, and real-time information make digital technologies an important tool for new urban governance. However, the initial hype of smart cities, big data and digital solutions is over. Today whole-of-society solutions are required which tell us more about the outcomes of specific institutional settings, the politics of participatory decision making, the workings of multilevel governance or new power structures from widespread digital technology use.

1.5 Urban futures, principles and research priorities

Quality of life and urbanization

How will urban futures (need to) look like under continuing urbanisation trends and within planetary boundaries? Can cities continue to grow and at the same time reduce their ecological footprint and improve it's residents' quality of life (QoL)? How can all live a good life (in cities) within planetary boundaries?⁹⁹

Although annual population growth rates are declining rapidly (0.9% in 2023) and global population growth is expected to peak in 2080 at around 10 billion¹⁰⁰, people are still moving into cities in hope of better opportunities and lives (Figure 16). In its [Atlas of the Human Planet](#), the European Commission estimates that 85% of all people on earth live in [urban areas](#).

Figure 16: Population trends of the world's largest cities.

Source: United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division (2018) and Our World in Data, <https://ourworldindata.org/urbanization>

Improving livelihoods in cities includes not only the provision of public services, health care and healthy urban environments. It requires us to rethink the quality of life of people living in cities and how cities are embedded into their ecological hinterlands and connected by economic and ecological lifelines of energy, resources and trade, which keep cities thriving.

Translating the idea of planetary boundaries to how cities are fueled and managed, requires transformative shifts in urban infrastructure and design, urban governance and urban life. According to the transformative shifts explained in previous chapters, for some cities improving the QoL of its residents means achieving more with more, while for others it means achieving more with less. Some cities require substantial investments into basic physical infrastructure development (roads, houses, sanitation, energy infrastructure), others need to

focus on improving their public service infrastructure (e.g., health care, transport, waste management), or urban design and architecture (e.g., urban green spaces, urban agriculture, public spaces, car-free zones), just to mention some.

Under the current framework of global agreements, all cities, however, will need to rethink how to improve the QoL within planetary boundaries. That means cities have a historical opportunity to take the lead in collaborating for managing the new global commons.

The QoL debate goes back several decades and has most prominently been triggered by the economist [Amartya Sen](#) and philosopher [Martha Nussbaum](#). Sen's central argument is that freedom and human agency are the primary drivers of development.¹⁰¹ Sen argues that freedom is good for development because it improves individuals' ability to help themselves: their agency and their capabilities. He breaks with the idea of progress as rising GDP, industrialization and technological progress and argues that enabling individual capabilities by freedom would lead people to live the kind of lives they have reason to value. Accordingly, poverty, is the deprivation of individual capabilities.

The shortcoming of his thesis is, however, that he asserts the role of the market and overlooks the importance of social institutions and powerful corporations. Essentially, his idea of development as freedom is capitalism with good values, trust and transparency. His thesis rests on a strong assumption of individualism and overlooks that when extended to the freedoms of transnational corporations and rich investors, communities can lose their capacities and capabilities and the market can constrain their freedoms. The privatisation of the water, energy and health sectors, in the name of liberalization, also meant that more people have become vulnerable to ill health, due to the lack of basic necessities.¹⁰²

The [Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity \(TEEB\)](#) also took up the question of how to measure the value of ecological goods and services, so that to prevent their destruction and overuse. The hope was that attaching an appropriate economic value to nature would prevent its overuse by creating a market: higher economic values would lead to lower demand, which meant less pressure on ecosystems. The idea had its limits because there are no market for many ecosystem goods and services and creating them, hypothetically or real (e.g., for carbon), did create an economic value but didn't solve the problem of their governance. In fact, in some cases even provided incentives for increased use.¹⁰³

One result of the TEEB initiative was to rethink measures of economic progress, which led to UNEP's support of the development of the Inclusive Wealth Index (IWI). The IWI is composed of indicators for natural, human and produced capital and the [Inclusive Wealth Report 2023](#) concludes that despite considerable wealth accumulation, especially in emerging economies, there is a global decline in Inclusive Wealth per capita. While most countries showed GDP growth and increases in total factor productivity (TFP), which, among others, helped to address SDG 1 (Poverty) and SDG 3 (Health and Wellbeing), the vast majority of countries experienced a natural capital reduction-related wealth decline. The most severe depletion of natural resources was found in countries with significant increases in TFP (over 5 per cent), such as Myanmar, Cambodia, Mozambique, Qatar, Chad and Chile.

The World Health Organization defines Quality of Life ([WHO QoL](#)) as “individuals’ perceptions of their position in life in the context of the culture and value system in which they live, and in relation to their goals, expectations, standards and concerns.” Others have defined urban QoL as the general well-being of people and societies living in cities and the quality of the (urban) environment in which they live^{104, 105} A wide range of urban QOL assessment tools has been developed to measure and monitor the quality of urban life taking into account the particular conditions of cities and the subjective and objective needs of their residents.

The OECD’s “How’s Life 2020” report¹⁰⁶ comes to the finding that more people (in OECD countries, most of them in cities) report high life satisfaction, they have more disposable income and feel safer. But medium household wealth is falling, inequality remains high and around 60% are exposed to unhealthy levels of air pollution. While, many of these QoL studies report certain levels exposure to environmental risks and inequality, they fail to connect these observations with ecological footprint, urban metabolism, or climate change studies.

Thereby they overlook the [core dilemma](#), which this global programme on urban health and wellbeing needs to address: the fact that improving health and wellbeing within cities comes at the expense of declining environmental and planetary health outside city boundaries, and the feedback effects this has on health and wellbeing inside cities. As mentioned earlier, the critical areas of food, water, energy security and antimicrobial resistance, relate to that [systemic dilemma of urban health and wellbeing](#).

Further, the simple inverted-U idea that when development (PPP/capita) reaches a certain point, inequality (Gini-coefficient) reduces and the idea of the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC), look like offering a solution to the dilemma by simply further economic growth, but both approaches do not take a systems approach.

The EKC, e.g., “only focuses on production and overlooks the impact of the consumption of imported goods on the environment. Consequently, environmental improvements from technological progress will be offset, and economic growth will result in more environmental degradation.”¹⁰⁷ The inverted U hypothesis overlooks the total costs (including externalities) at which wealth had been created and the costs of maintaining that wealth.

In this context it must be said that due to the first and second laws of thermodynamics, there are most likely no miracle solutions to the urban health and wellbeing dilemma – not even if energy would be for free. Solutions will most likely require more efforts, innovation, creativity, collaboration, energy and will lead to higher overall costs, but due to increasing efficiencies and population densities, it can be expected that wealth improvements will come at lower ecological and carbon footprints per capita.

In sum, QoL approaches to urban health and wellbeing need to adopt a systems approach and think outside the boundaries of the city. New national wealth and development progress measures are being developed and will be discussed at the [UN Summit of the Future](#). Cities will need to contribute to these new measures by assessing and delivering relevant data.

UN Habitat's World Cities Report 2022

In [UN Habitat's World Cities Report 2022](#), the word 'health' appears multiple times on 185 pages and chapter 7 is devoted to "Public Health and Sustainable Urban Futures." Ensuring the health of urban populations is still predominantly understood as preventing harm and disease, although a more holistic, systemic and intersectoral approach is increasingly adopted.

Health is increasingly understood as multilayered, intersectional phenomena, especially after the COVID pandemic which was a confirmation that due to land-use change, extraction and migration

activities, natural habitats became increasingly fragmented and thereby exposing the human-wildlife interface to novel infectious diseases.

Climate change is now considered the leading urban health threat. Floods can lead to rising levels of waterborne illnesses and increasing food insecurity. Apart from the economic burdens they cause, they can lead to injuries, deaths, and displacement. Droughts on the other hand already lead to an estimated 25 percent of cities globally facing water stress.

Traffic, dense buildings and limited green spaces lead to the urban heat island effect under which especially the elderly, children and other vulnerable groups suffer and an estimated 7 million people die prematurely due to urban air pollution.

The THRIVES framework (Pineo 2020)¹⁰⁸ is particularly relevant to a systems science programme on urban health and wellbeing. It advances health beyond the individual to the community, ecosystem and planetary health levels (Figure 17) and shows the layers of interconnected benefits when health is placed at the centre of urban planning and design. The framework reorients focus towards the existential threat of earth system boundaries and the social injustice created through inequitable and exclusive urban governance and design processes and outcomes. In contrast to other frameworks that start with individual characteristics, this framework positions planetary health at its core, shifting the focus from individuals to the environment.

"In 2019, the three leading causes of death globally were cardiovascular diseases, including strokes and ischaemic heart disease (IHD), respiratory diseases such as lower respiratory infections and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), and neonatal conditions, with 7 out of the 10 top causes due to NCDs (...). For the lowest-income nations, in 2019, the two leading causes of death were neonatal conditions and lower respiratory infections, followed by IHD and stroke; diarrhoeal diseases and malaria were ranked fifth and sixth. But across other regions, the leading cause of death is the same: ischaemic heart disease. "

[World Cities Report 2022](#): 217

Figure 17: Towards Health Urbanism: Inclusive Equitable Sustainable (THRIVES) framework (Pineo 2020)

Box 1: Key Messages of the World Cities Report 2022 on Public Health and Sustainable Urban Futures (UNHabitat 2022)

Taking the Health in All Policies approach, cities can make progress on multiple SDGs: By mainstreaming the Health in All Policies (HiAP) approach, cities can realize multiple benefits and unlock synergies between health and sustainable development pathways. Adding a health perspective in urban decision-making can simultaneously improve health (SDG 3), tackle poverty (SDG 1), foster gender equality (SDG 5) and enhance access to clean energy and climate-resilient infrastructure (SDGs 7 and 9).

Designing and implementing multisectoral approaches can realize healthy urban futures: A multisectoral approach is necessary because health is an essential component of sustainable urbanization given its impact on and interrelation with social, economic and environmental targets. Responsive, accountable local governments play a pivotal role in translating global and national targets to effective place-based interventions that generate multiple co-benefits for health, inclusion and climate change mitigation. Local governments, however, need stable funding, long-term political support and effective mechanisms for public engagement.

Ongoing disaggregated data collection is essential for effective responses to future urban health risks: Since urban health risks are multilayered and change rapidly, policymakers require ongoing data collection with attention to emerging and differentiated health challenges in urban areas. Using disaggregated data to inform inclusive interventions, policymakers can develop holistic multisectoral initiatives that address complex urban health inequities and support locally rooted solutions. City authorities can leverage digital technology such as telemedicine and drones, as well as community-led citizen science, to collect data from marginalized and hard-to-reach groups to ensure they leave no one behind.

Governments should provide universal health coverage to strengthen future health system preparedness: With the anticipation of future epidemics and pandemics, inequitable access to quality healthcare compromises the collective health and well-being for all. COVID-19 has unequivocally demonstrated that in an interconnected world, infectious diseases mock geographic, socioeconomic and other privilege boundaries. As part of the new social contract, governments should provide universal health coverage that secures equitable access as well as sufficient quality and affordability of healthcare for effective response to urban health crises in the future.

Addressing mental illness is an urgent priority not only for supporting health and dignity but also for continued economic and social development: Improving access to mental health programmes and developing holistic strategies to address mental illness remain a key concern globally, especially in the wake of COVID-19. Key priorities for equitable, inclusive mental health initiatives include additional investments that link mental health with universal health coverage and primary healthcare interventions. The new approach to mental health must move beyond biomedical techniques and instead seek to address the social determinants of health such as improving access to urban green spaces and enhancing social cohesion, as well as countering stigma facing those with mental illness.

Universal Principles: The Xiamen Call to Action

How can cities make their urban environments healthier and how can existing knowledge be put into action? In 2018, during a 2-day meeting in Xiamen, China, the International Science Council's science programme on Urban Health and Wellbeing (UHWB), in collaboration with Future Earth's Health Knowledge-Action Network (FE Health KAN), discussed those questions.

The Xiamen Call to Action¹⁰⁹ is an attempt to respond to the scale and rate of urbanisation which is threatening the health gains of the past century. Urbanisation represents the greatest ecological, social and technological transformation in human history.

If the global community is to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals before being overwhelmed by global change, the scope, scale, and ambition of transformative efforts need to accelerate. The authors of the [Xiamen Call to Action](#) recognize health as a web, inclusive of and interweaved with environmental, social, and economic factors. Human health shortcomings are manifestations of urban and planetary health ills, which is why marginal fixes of symptoms are likely to produce unwanted outcomes and high costs.

Further, the authors of the Xiamen Call, call for a systems approach to urban health and wellbeing which aims at managing urban complexity and a better understanding of the dynamic complexities of urban systems. Health experts, researchers, city planners and decision-makers agreed on the Xiamen Call for Action.

The call goes beyond a demand for more data or knowledge generation and highlights the need for integrated knowledge and governance to be fostered and applied in urban environments. It is based on the expertise and work in the urban health space by a range of different actors— representing the latest state-of-the-art on what is needed for urban health and wellbeing, and societal engagement. The Call for Action also recognises that urban and planetary health issues are systemically interconnected and accelerating, and leading to adverse health outcomes, in particular affecting vulnerable groups.

The type of knowledge needed to solve those challenges and problems requires that researchers work together and communicate their knowledge to decision makers in policy and civil society. Policymakers at all levels must also be encouraged, incentivized, and empowered to engage and foster an understanding of the nature of health in changing urban environments.

The authors suggest implementing the principles of the Xiamen Call by creating 'an urban (health) intelligence unit' (Brain of the City), which is part of an overall coherent urban governance system and measures and monitors success towards defined health and development goals. "National public health agencies often already assemble knowledge and expertise from various urban sectors and have the potential of implementing urban systems governance for health and wellbeing." That idea can be merged with call for creating [science missions](#).

The principles of building systems governance for urban health and wellbeing include:

1. Clear leadership and mandate to deal with urban health issues in an integrated manner.
2. Inclusiveness: including human rights; mutually beneficial for sectors.
3. Inter-spectrality: various urban sectors, such as transportation, energy, housing, including primary health care, work, and achieve urban health outcomes together.
4. Health and wellbeing as performance indicators which need to be measured centrally and locally.
5. Risk sharing: stakeholders investing in and benefiting from cross-sectorial collaboration also share the costs.
6. Pre-cautionary principle: it's about both the curative and preventive dimensions of health.

Localizing the New Urban Agenda by a Systems Approach to Urban Health and Wellbeing

The New Urban Agenda, adopted in 2016 in Quito, Ecuador during the Third UN Conference on Housing and Sustainable Urban Development (Habitat III), recognizes sustainability challenges that result from continued urbanization but also the potential of cities to improve health and wellbeing and contribute to sustainable development.

Due to continued urbanization, urban environments will be the context for sustainable development to be realised. Continued urbanization creates a dilemma: on the one hand, concentrating people in more compact cities makes them more energy efficient and provides people with health services and other opportunities which enable healthy lifestyles – on the other it also changes urban environments, leading to air, light, and noise pollution, rising inequalities, and changing food consumption and lifestyles, which have health deteriorating effects.

While providing a mandate to integrate health considerations into development and urban policies, the New Urban Agenda, lacks detail on the mechanisms and interventions required to achieve this¹¹⁰. This gap between what is known and implemented¹¹¹ is what the ISC global science programme on Urban Health and Wellbeing: a Systems Approach, aims at bridging by its goals and by promoting the idea [Data-Knowledge-Action Systems](#) for urban health and wellbeing.

Although the WHO's contribution to the New Urban Agenda takes a health sector perspective and focuses on "improving and protecting the health and wellbeing of citizens as core business of cities", it also establishes that mainstreaming health into all other urban policies

will have co-benefits in all other urban sectors. The World Health Organisation has made suggestions on how to implement the New Urban Agenda by taking an urban health approach in "[Health as a Pulse of the New Urban Agenda](#)".

The importance of combining 'human health' with a 'health in all policies' approach lies in the broadening of the concept of health. Whether integrating human health considerations into all urban policies, e.g. by health impact assessments, or extending the concept of health from the health sector to all other sectors, like planning, the economy or the environment, essentially does not make a difference and leads to the same urban health outcomes, which go beyond peoples' health in cities.

The concept of health thereby becomes "not only an indicator for monitoring progress, but a fundamental driver of sustainable development". Creating urban health "is about creating the conditions for urban residents to lead healthier, safer and more fulfilling lives" and the process of doing so itself is a contribution to the healthy functioning of cities.

This makes 'health' a unifying theme in urban planning and policy making and calls for a process which draws stakeholders with different views into a deliberation process about specific urban policies. It is for that reason that the World Health Organisation calls for "New models of cooperation and cross-sector collaboration (...) to identify synergies across these sectors and generate actions that result in overall gains to society, with health, environmental and economic co-benefits." (Health as the Pulse of the NUA)

A consolidated and coherent approach is required to implement the New Urban Agenda and the World Health Organisation sees that the health sectors in the position to synthesize knowledge and provide guidance about the health impacts of urban policies, plans and projects. Facilitated by the establishment of Urban Health Observatories that contribute to:

- promoting health-based targets for clean air, water, and energy systems
- providing guidance and guidelines on health implications of urban policies and monitoring and tracking health impacts of sector-based policies
- assessing the costs and health impacts of urban policies and decisions
- facilitating community engagement and strengthening the capacity for communicating the health implications of urban policies

The Data-Knowledge-Action model for urban health and wellbeing proposed under the research goal of this science plan aims at putting these suggestions into action.

In response to the evidence that decisions in cities are made despite a lack of data and evidence, numerous organisations have come together under UN Habitat's Quality of Life (QoL) initiative to develop indexes which measure the prosperity of cities:

- UN-Habitat City Prosperity Index
- Prosperity Index by the Regional Research Institute
- Legatum Prosperity Index
- Redefining Prosperity by the UN Sustainable Development Commission
- The sustainability of cities (European Union, UK)
- Sustainability City Index by Arcadis
- Sustainability Index by the I-ADB
- Creative City Index by Charles Landry
- Innovation Cities Index by 2thinknow
- Culture for development indicators, UNESCO

An important aspect of Data-Knowledge-Action Systems is to come to an understanding of what needs to be measured and for which purpose. These important questions need to be answered by people who participate in the knowledge co-creation process themselves. However, they have already been answered by experts who developed the [Urban Monitoring Framework \(UMF\)](#) (Figure 18): The data domains and indicators have been decided on and the purpose of the UMF is clear: it "harmonizes existing urban indexes and tools, and offers a universal framework that will be used to measure progress on the urban dimensions of the SDGs and the NUA.

The [Urban Monitoring Framework \(UMF\)](#) is useful in that it provides a set of criteria and indicators by means of which cities can assess their progress towards the SDGs and the NUA. The shortcomings lie in the lack of information about the systemic behaviour of the urban system, in the nature of an index and the knowledge-action gap it does not address. They are the reason the scientific committee of this UHWB programme decided to not create (yet another) index:

- An index conflates several indicators into one index which no longer informs about how cities solve the core [systemic dilemma of urban health](#) and wellbeing. Some cities can have good values for internal progress and quality of life and the index would not inform about the total costs at which these achievements have been made. It is possible, e.g. to derive a health index from selecting indicators from across the UMF matrix. But it is not possible to know which systemic connections exist to other domains within the city and to extra urban systems.
- The QoL index cannot inform about the systemic role of different indicators and their interconnectivity and impact on other system variables.

- The QoL index aims at monitoring progress towards globally agreed goals, specifically on the progress of the urban dimensions towards the SDG and NUA. Even though it is often assumed that local needs and wants are represented by the global goals, local goals may deviate from global goals, depending on specific initial local conditions. Their purpose may not be to contribute to global goals. Even local actors may not be aware of global goals and their own goals may not be conducive to global goals. The purpose of the UMF to monitor success towards SDG and NUA is primarily in the interest of those global organisations that work towards implementing those goals and cities that aim at assessing achievements towards those goals.
- The index UMF does not inform about cross-domain effects.
- The data required for building the index need to be collected by experts. The index is calculated by experts and handed over to urban decision makers who can use it for making better decisions, or not. The process of calculating the index and reporting on it, is not embedded into and part of the urban governance process. The information it provides can be used, or not.
- Developing an index may be informative, however it only partially contributes to building a Data-Knowledge-Action system. Especially the knowledge-action gap is not bridged.
-

Figure 18: Structure of the UMF

Source: [UMF, 2022](#)

WHO's Urban Health research priorities

Members of the Urban Health and Wellbeing programme contributed to the World Health Organisation's Urban Health Research Agenda (UHRA). To support member state with the implementation of their health, equity and sustainability targets, WHO has developed a set of global urban health research priorities for 2022–2032¹¹². The aim is to identify existing gaps in urban health research and then, by means of multisectoral interventions, improve the health of urban residents.

The [UHRA](#) overlaps with the science plan of the Urban Health and Wellbeing programme, especially with regards to adopting a systems approach, co-producing knowledge, moving towards sustainability and planetary health. The added value of having a global science programme is that it can facilitate the co-creation of innovative knowledge for a systems approach to urban health and wellbeing, not only in the domains of science but also for cities and urban stakeholder groups.

A global science programme on Urban Health and Wellbeing will be essential in communicating, promoting and seeking ways to implement the UHRA principles in cities.

Guiding principles for WHO's Urban Health Research Agenda (UHRA) are:

1. Adopting a Systems Approach
2. Co-production of knowledge
3. Equity
4. Cost-benefit and cost-effectiveness
5. Sustainability
6. Environmental impact and improvement of planetary health

The four research priorities of WHO's Urban Health Research Agenda and examples of research topics are listed in Table 2.

Table 2: WHO research priorities and examples of research topics

<p>Strengthening the links between urban health research and action</p>	<p>Mapping urban health interventions and their health impacts, exploring user-centered methodologies for more effective research and knowledge translation, appraisal of existing urban health funding and resource mobilization strategies, appraisal of evidence on institutions and mechanisms that improve equity in health service provision, innovative technologies for measuring urban health risks, document the use of health impact and assessment tools, appraise evidence for safeguarding health through its economic and commercial determinants, appraise models for citizen participation in urban health decision making, exploring approaches for integrating health into other urban agendas.</p>
<p>Building city-level evidence on the relationship between urban environments and health outcomes</p>	<p>Research on local governance approaches, social determinants of health, geographic disparities within cities and vector-borne diseases, access to health services, subjective perception of urban health risks, dose response models of the association between the urban exposome and health outcomes across the life-course, spatiotemporal models of the association between urban exposures and disease risk factors.</p>
<p>Generating evidence on under-research thematic areas</p>	<p>Climate change and urban health, combating health disinformation and misinformation, urban health emergencies, connections with Planetary Health and OneHealth research communities, strengthening the evidence on urban mental health, accidents and injuries in cities.</p>
<p>Generating evidence on under-researched urban population subgroups</p>	<p>Urban inequities, global data for monitoring and evaluating urban health, urban environmental change and health effects on marginalized groups and residents of informal settlements, people with disabilities, and the relationship between land use and zoning regulations on neighbourhood health inequities.</p>

PART 2 – Goals and Governance

2.1 Goals of a systems science programme on urban health and wellbeing

This science plan is an outcome of deliberations by the UHWB scientific committee members. It is mainly meant as a plan for action and guide from science for cities, city mayors, city council members and administrators, and urban communities- all who aim at improving urban health and wellbeing by taking a systems approach. It is also targeted at the interdisciplinary science communities working in the field of urban health and wellbeing, the academies of science, philanthropists and financial donors of science who promote implementation research for a systems approach to urban health and wellbeing.

There is a wide variation of systems approaches cities can take. The systems approach we promote here is characterized by:

1. conceptualizing the city in the context of the new urban sciences as complex social, ecological, and technological systems;
2. methodologically broadening the scope of methods (applied to the research of urban health and wellbeing) to include a wide range of modelling approaches;
3. choosing methods to investigate opportunities to improve urban health and wellbeing that are participatory and collaborative;
4. coupling data, knowledge and action into functioning Data-Knowledge-Action systems;
5. creating an urban health and wellbeing model in a specific urban context in the process of investigation and thereby creating systems intelligence for urban health and wellbeing;
6. connecting cities that apply systems approaches for urban health and wellbeing for mutual learning.

While the [goal for research](#) defines thematic priorities and data needs, the knowledge and action related goals create the “science” of urban health and wellbeing.

The following science-action goals have been defined by the programme’s scientific committee¹¹³:

1. Research urban health and wellbeing topics by applying systems methods and the urban health and wellbeing model
2. Promote Health in all policies and urban decision making
3. Science-policy discourse and communication on a systems approaches to UHWB
4. Training, education and dissemination of knowledge
5. Networking, cooperation and knowledge exchange among researchers and urban communities of practice.

Overarching goal

The overarching goal is to enhance cities' systems intelligence for a better understanding of the complexities of urban environments in which opportunity spaces for urban health and wellbeing can be created within planetary boundaries.

In short, to enhance cities' systems intelligence for urban and planetary health.

By systems intelligence we mean “...*intelligent behaviour in the context of complex systems involving interaction and feedback. (...) By observing (a city's) own interdependence in the feedback intensive environment, (the city) is able to act intelligently*”.¹¹⁴

Systems intelligence becomes relevant when, like in the current global change context, the relationships between social and ecological systems change and require a behavioural response in order to survive. When the development and growth which has led to health and wellbeing, causes a degree of environmental decline that undermines health and wellbeing, behaviours needs to change (Figure 19).

A global programme on systems science for urban health and wellbeing provides a framework within which systems intelligence for urban health and wellbeing can be built.

Figure 19: Enhancing cities' systems intelligence for urban health and wellbeing means developing

data-knowledge-action systems to better understand the mutual relationship between human, urban and planetary health.

In 2020, the scientific committee of the UHWB programme has identified the following sub-goals for achieving the overarching goal:

1. Promote Health in All Policies and implement the [Xiamen Call for Action](#)
2. Research on Data-Knowledge-Action Systems for healthy urban environments
3. Communicate the systems approach for urban health and wellbeing
4. Develop training and education material as well as collaborative systems modelling
5. Build collective intelligence by networking and cooperating with cities, intragovernmental and civil society organisations

In the following sections, the relevance of each goal will be explained and how a global systems science programme envisions the implementation of the goals. The implementation of the goals can only be achieved by a commitment to global collaboration for urban health and wellbeing. That requires engagement by relevant stakeholder groups to demonstrate how the goals are implemented in cities and municipalities around the world.

Relevant main stakeholder groups for implementing the UHWB goals are:

- Goal 1: All decision-making levels in cities, municipalities and at national level.
- Goal 2: Academies of science, universities and other research organisations, research groups or individual researchers, and financial donors of research and action for urban health and wellbeing
- Goal 3: The international programme office to disseminate findings, organise events, mediate discussions; the scientific committee members and their institutions to introduce the systems approach taken by the programme; the sponsors of the programme to connect to other global science programmes and include the programme in the relevant global deliberations; civil society organization in their specific projects.
- Goal 4: The international programme office to organise seminars and plan trainings, e.g. the MOOC on Healthy Urban Systems and the UHWB summer school; the scientific committee members and their institutions to integrate lessons learnt and innovative approaches in their lectures and classes.
- Goal 5: The international programme office and its partners in science and practice to build networks, and organise conferences. Here, in particular city and science/research networks should be collaborating more frequently.

Goal 1: Promote Health in All Policies and implement the Xiamen Call for Action

The Health in All Policies approach (HiAP) is based on the awareness that the determinants that create health often lie outside the traditional public health or healthcare sectors and that these determinants are systemically interconnected and constitute wicked problems or problems of complexity¹¹⁵. Integrating health goals into policies for all urban sectors can create co-benefits¹¹⁶ and reduce costs from siloed and fragmented urban governance.

For that reason better coordination and collaboration between agencies can help identify shared goals across sectors, build better infrastructure, create collective and systems intelligence and create higher efficiency and accountability in policy-making for urban health and wellbeing.

The World Health Organization (WHO) has been driving the [Health in All Policies](#) (HiAP) initiative and its roots go back to the origins of the WHO itself. At the 8th Global Conference on Health Promotion, Helsinki, Finland, (10-14 June 2013), the Helsinki statement on Health in All Policies (WHO 2014) had been agreed on. At that meeting the participants called on governments to commit to health and health equity as a political priority and announced:

“... Health in All Policies is an approach to public policies across sectors that systematically takes into account the health implications of decisions, seeks synergies, and avoids harmful health impacts in order to improve population health and health equity. It improves accountability of policymakers for health impacts at all levels of policy-making. It includes an emphasis on the consequences of public policies on health systems, determinants of health and wellbeing. We recognize that governments have a range of priorities in which health and equity do not automatically gain precedence over other policy objectives. We call on them to ensure that health considerations are transparently taken into account in policy-making, and to open up opportunities for co-benefits across sectors and society at large.”

In its previous phase the UHWB programme has facilitated collaborative modelling workshops which brought urban stakeholders together to deliberate on how to approach the most pressing urban health and wellbeing issues in their cities or communities. The collaborative modelling workshops not only informed stakeholders of the complex and interconnected nature of the problems they were facing; they offered a platform and a systematic way of investigating, deliberating and, in that process, building collective systems intelligence.

With the support of the regional office of the International Science Council, from 2015-2016, the UHWB programme co-organised a workshop which brought mayors of major cities in El Salvador together to discuss the HiAP approach.

The result was the Urban Health Model of El Salvador (Modelo de Salud Urbana) which was presented in June 2017 by the El Salvadorian Ministry of Health (MINSAL) as an essential component of its health reform and is now adopted also by other countries in the region. The model generated an extensive consultation process including inputs from public institutions and civil society organizations, as well as the global science program on Urban Health and Wellbeing, which was launched under the International Science Council (ISC).

Strengthening the science-policy partnership – T20

Another example for promoting the HiAP initiative is the engagement of the UHWB programme with the Global Solutions Initiative (GSI) and its core community T20. The GSI envisions, proposes and evaluates policy responses and solutions to major global problems. Urbanization, environment and health have been identified as major issues of concern.

Two of the policy areas addressed by the GSI are specifically on health: 1) Global health and COVID-19, 2) Health and social transformation. Three GSI engagement groups also overlap with the mandate of the UHWB programme: Science20 (S20), Think20 (T20) and Urban20 (U20).

Most relevant for the UHWB programme is the GSI's vision on recoupling. The UHWB programme aims at recoupling human, urban and planetary health, so that health and wellbeing of people and cities does not come at the expense of planetary health and global sustainability goals. The GSI argues that economic prosperity, environmental performance and social prosperity are decoupled in many countries and that recoupling needs to happen in areas of:

- a) Solidarity. The Social Solidarity Index is composed of Inward Solidarity and Outward Solidarity. Inward Solidarity reflects social support received by friends and family. Outward Solidarity is composed of Giving behavior, satisfaction with efforts to deal with the poor, and a Minority rights index.
- b) Agency. Involves empowerment and covers people's need to influence their fate through their own efforts. The Agency Index has four components: Confidence in empowering institutions Index, Freedom of life choice, Vulnerable employment and Life expectancy.
- c) Material gain. Could be measured by Gross Domestic Product per capita.
- d) Environmental sustainability. Measured by the Environmental Performance Index

Recoupling is about connecting human and social capital capacities with the challenges we are facing. Wellbeing therefore depends on continuous effort to recouple capacities with challenges. The UHWB

programme is proposing a concrete recouping mechanism called the “[Data-Knowledge-Action System](#)” and described in detail under Goal 2 of this science plan.

Recoupling addresses the same dilemma which the UHWB programme is addressing by putting a salutogenic health concept into practice: the dilemma that long-lasting health and wellbeing of cities cannot be achieved at the expense of planetary health and the need of a (recoupling) mechanisms that balances human, urban and planetary health.

The idea of recoupling must also be understood in the context of the 1st law of cybernetics (Ashby’s law or the law of requisite variety)¹¹⁷. W. Ross Ashby, a British cybernetician worked on the concept of homeostasis and was interested in how complex system operate in changing environments. The law suggests that the internal diversity of any self-regulating system, such as an organization, or a city must match the variety and complexity of its environment if it is to deal with the challenges posed by that environment. If the systems that regulate do not have enough (or requisite) variety to match the complexity of the regulated, then the system will be out of control.¹¹⁸ The same law has been applied by Ostrom in search of institutional arrangement for governing the commons.¹¹⁹

G20¹²⁰ is an intergovernmental forum that unites major economies of the world: 19 individual countries and two regional blocs: the European Union (EU) and the African Union (AU). Together, these members represent around 85% of the global GDP and two-thirds of the world's population.

The T20 of the GSI provides intellectual support for the G20. The [T20](#) builds bridges between the policy recommendations of successive G20 Presidencies, between researchers and policymakers, between researchers and private sector implementers and between successive generations of thought leaders. The G20 Insights Platform of the GSI offers policy proposals to the G20, produced by Task Forces from the [Think20 \(T20\) Group](#), the Global Solutions Initiative’s [Council for Global Problem-Solving](#) as well as experts from renowned [think tanks](#).

The GSI is inherently solution driven. It generates cutting edge Policy Briefs for the policy leaders of the G20 and other international associations. Decision-makers from policy-making, business and civil society contribute to the formulation of relevant policy proposals and provide a crucial bridge between the recommendations generated by the research institutions and their implementation.

Health in All Policies (HiAP) and governance

Urban health can be considered a microcosm of global health (as stated in the slogan of [urbanhealth360](#)) and urban health governance is an important regulatory mechanism to achieve sustainable development globally. According to the UN, “[Our struggle for global](#)

[sustainability will be won or lost in cities](#)". Global urban health governance is at the heart of sustainable development, and it is at a turning point in human history: from development progress, measured in GDP and achieved by cheap energy, and at the expense of planetary health (the economy of a small world on a big planet), to an economy of a big world on a small planet (Figure 1). Now, health and wellbeing needs to be created within earth system boundaries. Development progress which has negative social and environmental repercussions outside urban boundaries is no longer an affordable option.

Figure 20: Bowen et al (2012) suggest a systems-based and intersectoral approach to (urban) health governance in response to climate change. The diagram shows the institutions and sectors (outer circles) relevant to the health effects of climate change.

Governance is concerned with how decisions are made and actions are taken and is therefore essential for an adaptive urban health and wellbeing strategy, e.g., for climate change. The health sector closely links to other sectors and organisations when it comes to the health effects of climate change, which also explains the [Health in All Policies](#) approach (Figure 20).

In order to develop effective adaptation strategies to reduce the health effects of climate change, multi-layered and collaborative/participatory governance styles are recommended that support collective action (Bowen et al 2012).¹²¹ In order to adequately respond to this challenge, urban health governance requires systemic innovations which enable cities to adequately respond to global environmental changes.

The UHWB programme provides a framework for research in which urban governance innovations need to capture critical data about a city's metabolism, liveability and health, transform those data into knowledge about a city's systemic health condition and environmental impact, reform existing urban governance structures and institutional arrangements that clearly define the responsibilities of actors and enterprises in both public and private sectors, and eventually identify entry points for adaptive action. Goal 2 presents a framework for an urban health adaptive governance research project.

Goal 2: Research on Data-Knowledge-Action Systems for Healthy Urban Environments

In support of the overarching goal of this framework, the research agenda for urban health and wellbeing shall be transdisciplinary, implementation-, solutions-, and [mission-oriented](#). Such a research agenda primarily aims at assisting urban communities and cities to identify and solve actual problems related to urban health and wellbeing within planetary boundaries.

Based on the realisation that the global Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) will not be achieved unless deep, structural transformations across all sectors in society happen, and inspired by Sachs et al. (2019)¹²² proposed transformations, the International Science Council (ISC)¹²³ has suggested that science should be [mission-oriented](#) and needs to make a bold move to fill the gap between science and policy and science and action to actively create and change the conditions required for transformative changes.

According to the International Science Council (ISC) (ibid), the science community should do so by being “constantly engaged in the necessary extra-scientific, societal mobilization to act on co-produced knowledge advances (...) (by) engag(ing) in the policy process (...) and changing the fundamental conditions that hold systems in place.” These conditions include policies, practices, resource flows, relationships/connections, power dynamics, and mindsets.

Mission oriented science for a systems science programme on urban health and wellbeing aims at contributing to the global goals by producing systems intelligence at the urban community scale and at a human scale. It aims at promoting the systems intelligence required for urban communities to identify their urban health and wellbeing issues and address them in a collaborative, collective intelligence generating process.

The [human scale](#) of urban health and wellbeing is created in urban environments which are conducive for people to satisfy their human needs without compromising the ecological foundations on which the provision of need satisfiers depends. Many approaches to human scale urban development have been taken, e.g., in urban planning.¹²⁴

The collaborative modelling approach suggested as part of the [Data-Knowledge-Action systems](#), is able to identify synergistic satisfiers which relate to the [co-benefits of urban health and wellbeing](#). Synergistic satisfiers are interventions that are highly interconnected with other system components.

For finding the human scale of urban health and wellbeing it is necessary to re-think what it means to be human in cities on a planet with boundaries. Accordingly, the combination of satisfiers with all their downstream implications needs to be designed by urban communities in their specific cultural, social, political, ecological and historical context.

Research for urban health and wellbeing must go beyond the question of what makes people in cities healthy, or which combination of factors contribute to health and wellbeing from living in cities. In addition to that, it must address the fundamental problem of sustainability, which is that health and wealth can be created in cities but at the expense of environments outside the urban boundaries.

The new urban science therefore perceives cities as complex living systems extending to peri-urban environments. Cities are largely unaware of their own health status and the impact they have on people and the environment. While increasing amounts of data and methods are available today an integrated urban environmental health assessment and corresponding rapid response tool is still missing: an urban data-knowledge-action tool.

Potential research questions and objectives

How can cities create knowledge on the health of urban environments by better balancing human wellbeing with environmental health? The [systemic dilemma](#) cities are in, is that the health and wellbeing they create for people come at the expense of environmental health. The costs of creating the urban advantage are often being externalized. Cities do not keep account of the health impacts they have on people and the environment, and they lack a rapid response tool to help avoiding them.

Despite being engines of economic growth and innovation, which creates wealth within urban boundaries, cities are free riding on the planetary commons and they make insufficient use of existing data and methods to measure, model and manage their health impact on people and the environment.

The argument for research on Data-Knowledge-Action systems for healthy urban environments is that the lack of data-knowledge-action systems prevents cities from knowing about their impact on human and environmental health and making appropriate decisions to transform towards Healthy Urban Environments. The aim, however is NOT to merely collect ever more data, rather, the right data, which enables people to better monitor and manage their cities. Better knowledge co-creation processes can thereby often replace the need for ever more data. The goal is to develop and test a tool which strengthens a city's capacity and systems intelligence to determine its urban health condition and impact on people and the environment and at the same time empower people to co-create their cities.

The objective of a potential research is to develop a data-knowledge-action model (Figure 21) and protocol which enables cities to measure, monitor, model and manage the health impact they have on people and their proximal and distal environments, and to test it.

The tool will improve a city's capacity for evidence-based policy making for people's wellbeing and environmental health and its capacity to respond to the pressures of increasingly urgent decision making under conditions of uncertainty, contested values in the context climate change and earth system boundaries.

Methodology and novelty

The city is the unit of analysis of urban-environmental systems which need to balance the health of its people and the environment. For that a city requires data-knowledge-action systems to identify opportunity spaces for sustainable nature-, technology-, or community-based solutions.¹²⁵

Working steps for a potential research project aim at establishing such data-knowledge-action system and testing it on a specific case:

1. Defining the boundaries of the system and describing the model
2. Identifying the critical system components/indicators/variables which determine population, urban and environmental health of the system and the data needed to describe them.
3. Collecting data on population-, urban- and environmental health, incl. data from remote sensing, urban metabolism, ecological footprint studies.
4. Building a systems model. Defining the interconnectedness of system components and their impact on another.
5. Carrying out simulations, policy tests and sensitivity analysis to determine current health impacts on people and the environment, future interventions and policies.
6. Developing a prototype of a real-time data-knowledge-action system tool.
7. Dissemination: publish results and organise science-policy dialogues with decision makers and stakeholders.

Figure 21: Data-Knowledge-Action Model for Urban Health and Wellbeing: Balancing human and planetary health by a transdisciplinary, collaborative systems science approach. Conceptual model for a “Healthy Urban Environments” research proposal

The novelty of this research results from the combination of urban computing and participatory systems modelling and the development of a data-knowledge-action decision support tool. The method uses measurable data and expert knowledge to solve the problems with conventional big data-driven solutions which complicate, not ease decision making, by including stakeholders in the problem-solving process.

The outputs of the research are 1) the method as tool, 2) results for selected urban case studies. Feasibility is ensured by making use of available data and established methods for modelling, analysis, and forecasting. Data categories come from biocybernetic categories: population health (social, physical, mental), urban health (urban metabolism) and environmental/planetary health (food, water, energy, waste, emissions, pollution, heat, urban green and land use).

Data from remote sensing, urban metabolism studies, ecological footprint analysis and population health assessments will be used. Optical remote sensing in high spatial/temporal resolutions, measures urban environments and anthropogenic impact. Urban health related CO₂, NO₂ levels can be assessed and indicate greenness, moisture, and heat.

Data from quantitative urban metabolism (UM) accounting aim to identify the major sources of pollution, energy use, heat radiation, food waste and emitters of greenhouse gases. We will focus on data, for which FAIR principles apply.

Collaborative urban systems modelling (Figure 22) makes use of the previously collected data for defining, calibrating and running the model. It is similar to community-based systems modelling ([Hovmand, 2014](#)). Here we map the systemic state of an urban environment, e.g. by systemic role diagrams (Figure 24), carry out policy tests, sensitivity analyses and simulations (forecasting).

Figure 22: The flow from data to knowledge and action in the collaborative modelling process for urban health and well being that does not compromise planetary health.

During the programme’s scientific committee meeting Nov 28-30, 2023 the committee members discussed whether it would be useful to develop an urban health and wellbeing index which could be calculated for cities worldwide. The committee came to the conclusion, that an index would not be able to appropriately capture and represent a city’s health and wellbeing, as these are two systemically linked and sometimes counteracting measures, which conflate in an index. While an index similar to the Inclusive Wealth Index seems to be attractive at the urban level, the index would conflate different indicators into one index which would no longer say anything about a city’s health and wellbeing and therefore would have limited use in policy making. Alternatively, it was suggested to develop radar diagrams for cities similar to that shown in Figure 23.

Figure 23: Diagram of the Healthy City score for Amsterdam Port ^{126, 127}

Figure 24: The systemic role for each system variable is defined by its interconnectedness with other variables and can be more or less active, critical buffering (passive) or reactive.¹²⁸

Scientific impact

Cities are ill equipped to rapidly respond to impacts from climate change by assessing their impact on the health of people and the environment. This project will define critical data needs and develop a tool to assess the health of urban environments and provide decision support.

The main scientific impacts from research on Data-Knowledge-Action Systems on Healthy Urban Environments, results from: 1) developing a tool from a scientific method and 2) co-creating knowledge on specific urban environments.

Urban health assessment, modelling and decision support tools for managing urban environments, visualize population and environmental health impacts (systemic impact, radar diagrams) and close the following gaps in urban science and policy:

The **methodological gap** refers to the novelty of this research and is about the combination of population health assessment and remote sensing studies with complex urban systems modelling.

The **knowledge gap** between science and practice/policy is bridged. Collecting data, creating knowledge and acting on urban environmental health issues is no longer done exclusively in the science domain. By means of [collaborative systems modelling](#), stakeholders themselves participate in building and calibrating the model, and evaluating the outcomes.

The **action gap** is closed by developing the data-knowledge-action tool and providing training for developing the tool. With such rapid response tool cities can better measure, monitor and manage their urban environments and are able to choose better adaptation and mitigation actions.

The **international collaboration gap** is bridged when cities who apply the approach will benefit from exchanging knowledge on Healthy Urban Environments with other cities and international city networks.

Goal 3: Communicate the Systems Science Approach to Urban Health and Wellbeing

Science communication has been defined as “any information exchange designed to engage targeted audiences in conversations or activities related to science, technology, engineering, mathematics, and medicine (STEMM) topics”¹²⁹ Finlay et al. (2021)¹³⁰ define the work of science communication as a “journey of iterative, endless cycles of reflection and practice to co-develop inclusive, relevant, equitable and useful science communication, together.”

In a world which is deeply divided, even on the topic of what constitute scientific facts, it is not only important to carry out the science for urban health and wellbeing but also to communicate it. Doing the science and communicating science are systemically linked.

Here we look at the specific case of communicating systems science for urban health and wellbeing for each of the above-mentioned target groups. The science process aims at creating knowledge for solving specific problems and the process of science communication serves the twin goals to 1) share and disseminate (inform) that knowledge, but also 2) to co-create it.

Communicating systems science for urban health and wellbeing means not only conveying information or creating specific media content for a specific audience, by addressing it to them and using language that speaks to them. More importantly, it means to also include stakeholders in the science co-production process and talk with them.

This is a challenge for those who work inside the science domain because they need to be aware of the mental models and the jargon, they use which often needs to be explained, translated, agreed on or simply avoided, in order to be able to communicate. On the other hand stakeholders outside the science domain can learn how scientists think, articulate problems and actively contribute how this is done.

Common goals and shared values of those who communicate and co-create science, help making the communication process more efficient and effective (in the sense that it leads to outcomes or decisions faster). However, efforts should also be made to create communication environments that are a safe place for expressing critical or controversial voices, and to avoid too much uncritical, agreeable and confirmative voices for the sake of moving the conversation forward.

The process of science communication for urban health and wellbeing should be designed to match the nature of the problem it addresses and therefore, in the case of urban health and wellbeing, needs to be genuinely participatory, inclusive, reflexive and deliberative.¹³¹ The proposal made under goal 2, which outlines a potential systems science approach, is consistent with how science communication is characterized in this section.

Thereby, the ways in which knowledge is co-created by science communication, also defines the choice of methods for scientific inquiry and they determine the ways in which social learning takes place and which types of governance are applied to act on the knowledge which has been created. The ways in which knowledge is created and communicated strongly links

to the ways in which knowledge is acted on and how actions are governed. This obviously links to the [post-normal science](#) approach and to the [politics of uncertainty](#).

Science communication for urban health and wellbeing is also closely related to science diplomacy. [Science diplomacy](#) is neither only about policy advice by scientists to urban policy makers; nor is it only about the use of science to advance diplomatic goals.¹³²

Although **science diplomacy** eludes a commonly agreed definition it is generally understood to include the following three aspects:

- 1) Diplomacy for science – the use of diplomatic action to facilitate international scientific collaboration, e.g. by negotiating R&D agreements and exchange programmes or enabling the establishment of international research infrastructures.
- 2) Science for diplomacy – the use of science as a soft power to advance diplomatic objectives, e.g. for building bridges between nations and creating good will on which diplomatic relations can be built.
- 3) Science in diplomacy – the direct support of diplomatic processes through science, e.g. by providing scientific advice and evidence to inform and support decision-making in foreign and security policies.

Often science diplomacy is presented as a panacea for solving grand global challenges. Rungius and Fink (2020)¹³³ criticize that understanding of science diplomacy as solutionistic. Scientific methodology and rationality can be a valuable contribution to problem-solving, however, as mentioned in previous paragraphs, problem solving for urban health and wellbeing is a multi-stakeholders process in which scientists and policy makers can make a valuable contribution, among other stakeholders. Further, the nature of the (complex) problem should define the method used to solve it, as has been explained in reference to [Ashby's Law](#), which is why complexity reducing methods are, per se, not always ideal. The authors (ibid) further caution the overly optimistic expectations towards science diplomacy because the discourse often misconceives ideals and norms for real and because science can easily be instrumentalised for political purposes and become politicized, which can have unwanted consequences, as could be observed during the COVID pandemic.^{134, 135, 136}

On the other hand a transdisciplinary science approach calls for science to become politically engaged. The International Science Council argues that there is an increasing need to bring scientists closer to non-academic actors and stakeholders to solve problems of increasing complexity – an argument which is also brought forward by the proponents of a post-normal science approach.^{137, 138}

Science diplomacy for urban health and wellbeing can be put into practice by seeking and cultivating the dialogue between scientists, urban policy-makers, private sector representatives and other stakeholders, like at the [Guangzhou Award for Urban Innovation](#). Cities are innovation hubs and early adopters of emerging technologies and they can take the lead in promoting a multi-stakeholder dialogue, like, e.g. [the Barcelona Science and Technology Diplomacy Hub](#).

Goal 4: Develop Training and Education Material on Systems Science for Urban Health and Wellbeing

Over the period of the past 5 years the UHWB programme has designed and implemented a Massive Open Online Course on [Healthy Urban Systems Part 1](#) and [Part 2](#), hosted by Lausanne University, Switzerland and run on the Coursera platform.

In its [podcast series](#), the UHWB programme invited international organizations, urban planning and governance thought leaders and urban health scientists who have worked and have been associated with the programme to share their knowledge, insights, views and outlooks, and to seek ways for collaborating and implementing a transdisciplinary science agenda for cities', peoples' and planetary health.

Apart from publishing scientific papers, the science and practice of a systems approach to urban health and wellbeing can be made part of the curricula of higher and lower education institutions. Private companies are already in the business of facilitating workshops on collaborative modelling for urban health and wellbeing. That knowledge can be used to train knowledge multipliers by training trainers on collaborative systems modelling for urban health and wellbeing.

The ultimate aim of pursuing this goal is to enable urban communities to create the knowledge they need to transform urban systems for urban health and wellbeing.

Goal 5: Build Collective Intelligence by Networking and Cooperating with Cities, Intragovernmental and Civil Society Organisations

A transdisciplinary commitment in science for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals, cannot be effective unless science and policy communities work together more closely. It requires not only the science community to adopt methods that include and speak to policy makers, but also policy- and decision makers' willingness to participate and to devote time and resources for the continuous co-creation of urban health and wellbeing intelligence and action.

The ISC in its proposal to establish [science missions](#) has been rather progressive in suggesting that mission-oriented science needs to change the fundamental conditions that hold unsustainable and unjust systems in place. In order to do so those systems need to be understood first in order to identify the most effective and efficient levers for systems change. That is where this programme can provide support to urban communities.

Currently there is a large mismatch between the goals of international science programmes and their mandate to address shared goals for sustainable development and the availability of multi-lateral science funding.

This goal ties the previous goals together. Building collective intelligence requires advancing the system science of Urban Health and Wellbeing, it needs to implement the knowledge

created and it requires the constant engagement of all stakeholders. Under this goal the UHWB programme needs to create **new alliances** for knowledge co-creation, knowledge exchange and knowledge implementation. This requires financial resources specifically designated to transdisciplinary and implementation-oriented systems science for urban health and wellbeing, for cities and with cities.

An open call for expressions of interest to become UHWB collaborating center can be launched under this goal. One example for a collaboration project with an Ecuadorian non-government organisation is the Urban Health Forum established by [LIDE](#) ([Box 2](#)).

Box 2: Urban Health Forum in Ecuador

Metropolitan areas and urban communities have to deal with issues such as maintaining public spaces, collecting waste and providing access to health clinics. As their population grows, so does the indispensability of public health services and opportunities to live healthy lives in cities. However, due to financial resource scarcity interventions need to prioritize actions which are most relevant to all stakeholders and add value to public health. In order to better understand the health impacts of uncluttered parks or clean sidewalks, or access to electric public transport, researchers at the Ecuadorian Development Research Lab (Laboratorio de Investigación para el Desarrollo del Ecuador - LIDE) approached these and similar questions by taking a systems approach as promoted by the International Science Council's Urban Health and Wellbeing Programme, and established the first Urban Health Forum in Ecuador. Headquartered in Guayaquil. LIDE is an independent research centre that studies issues regarding education, health, the environment and governance in order to influence policy making processes.

In collaboration with the Urban Health and Wellbeing Programme, LIDE is setting up the Urban Health Forum which will provide a transdisciplinary platform for local policymakers, citizens, scientists, civil society organizations and other stakeholders to understand urban health challenges, deliberate with communities and formulate common policy agendas. Urban health is more than just providing healthcare services. The goal is to bring multiple sectors together in a place where diverse perspectives and collaborative efforts can lead to science-based solutions to the most pressing issues regarding a city's health and its resident's wellbeing. The Forum is also an opportunity for civil society, the public and private sector to establish long-lasting partnerships and trust that will enhance cooperation with municipal decision makers. For the sake of reducing regional disparities, LIDE is looking to establish the Forum's headquarters outside of Quito and Guayaquil (Ecuador's two main urban areas) and has already held discussions with elected local representatives as well as academia to do so.

2.2 Proposed governance of a global programme on systems science for urban health and wellbeing

Shifting from a science programme that takes a systems approach to urban health and wellbeing, to a systems science programme on urban health and wellbeing implies and requires that scientists from both domains, the health and the urban sciences, work closer together. It also requires a closer link between the science, policy and action communities.

The governance of a global programme on systems science for urban health and wellbeing is shaped towards the purpose to co-create knowledge and implement it in urban planning, health and sustainable development. The Health in All Policies concept and the universal principles identified in the [Xiamen Call for Action](#) are important in shaping the governance structure of a global programme on systems science for urban health and wellbeing.

The governance structure and process of the programme could resemble the conceptual structure of a [Data-Knowledge-Action system](#).

Structural components of the programme are:

- The main body and sponsor
- The co-sponsors
- The scientific committee
- The international programme office
- The executive director
- The partners and collaborators

The **initiator** and ‘main body’ of the programme: The International Science Council (ISC). The UHWB programme is an affiliated body of the ISC. ISC is co-sponsors and lends its support to the programme.

Co-sponsors of the programme should represent 1) the science community at large, represented by the initiator and main body of the programme, 2) the health (science and practice) communities, 3) the urban (science and practice) communities, and 4) the system science and practice communities.

Representatives from each community can be from professional organisations or civil society organisations. Each representative would be tasked to guide and support the programme with professional expertise and connections to networks and key stakeholders from the science, policy or civil society communities. Further they would ensure that the programme decides on actions which advance towards the overall goal. All sponsors of the programme are also scientific committee members. They act according to the Terms of Reference for the programme sponsors.

The **scientific committee (SC)** consists of around 10 professionals who hold knowledge on relevant thematic areas of the programme. They act according to the Terms of Reference for SC members.

The **International Programme Office** provides logistic support for all actions decided on by the SC. It organizes the SC meetings, participates in them and manages the programme budget provided by the host organization for the IPO.

The **executive director (ED)** of the programme is head of the International Programme Office, with support of the IPO, the SC and the sponsors, organizes the scientific committee meetings and executes the decisions made by the SC. The ED should have the interdisciplinary academic qualifications to speak to each of the communities participating in the programme, and the seniority to communicate with stakeholders from the policy domain in diverse cultural and all political contexts.

Partners and collaborators. The programme works with a network of partners and collaborators implementing the recommendations of the SC and making use of the programme’s framework to carry out specific projects which demonstrate how urban health and wellbeing can be achieved by taking a systems approach. Collaborating organisations are endorsed by the programme.

Figure 25: Governance of the UHWB programme. In pursuit of its overarching goal, the UHWB scientific committee (SC) receives information about urban health and wellbeing issues of concern to urban communities and stakeholders. Scientific deliberations are held on how the issue can be conceptualized within the overall systems science framework and which methods can be best applied to solve a problem or achieve a particular goal. Strategic deliberations are then held on the question of what is needed to implement the systems approach and who are the key players. More generally the SC also defines research priorities and decides on how, when and in which fora to promote, disseminate and discuss them.

3 Conclusions

This science plan serves as a theoretical and conceptual framework for the International Science Council's Programme on Urban Health and Wellbeing: a Systems Approach. It explains the basic concepts and definitions needed for a second 10-year phase of the programme, as agreed by the International Science Council and the programme's host, the Institute of Urban Environment, Chinese Academy of Sciences. The plan deviates from the first 10-year plan by putting a stronger focus on the urban aspects of urban health and wellbeing. While human health in cities remains important, the new urban health approach recognizes that cities can not only function in service of people's health. As complex systems, they need to balance the health of people and the planet.

As outlined in this science plan, a new systems science for urban health and wellbeing is in the making and a global programme on the matter has moved us further into the direction of better understanding and solving problems of high complexity, urgency and uncertainty related to human, urban and planetary health. Further, while the science of health, the science of cities and the systems sciences are progressing, more decisive steps need to be taken in communicating the systems science approaches to urban health and wellbeing and demonstrating its solution solving capacity by facilitating its application.

Today, the matter of urban health and wellbeing within planetary boundaries remains highly relevant, scientifically, environmentally and for society. It matters not only for most of the earth's human population living in cities, but also for the sustainability of planetary health, which is a precondition for living healthy lives in cities. The relevant matter is not only about health and wellbeing in cities. Equally important is how it is conceptualized and approached by the systems approach outlined in this document which is less dominated by the anthropocentric determinants of health idea and more by the idea that urban health is an emergent property of complex urban systems. Urban health is not only about the health of people living in cities, it is about the healthy functioning of urban systems, embedded into ecosystems of the planet's biosphere.

Together with the global context, the problem-solving context for science has also changed. For problems characterized by conflicting values, urgency of decision-making and uncertainty, typical for urban health problems, it is no longer sufficient to apply the normal scientific method. A shift to post-normal science has therefore been proposed.

In the past, urban health researchers have mainly been looking at multiple social and environmental determinants of urban health, thereby overlooking the one most important determinant, which is the way we look, or the determinants of how knowledge for urban health is created. Our knowledge of the possible causes of ill health, or poverty, e.g., is vast, and yet we are lagging behind in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals. Researchers too often forget that their means of observation and the experimental design, influence what they observe and find. The conventional, evidence-based science approach might not go far enough for creating the knowhow to solve the problems at hand. A shift from 'knowing what' to 'knowing how' has therefore been suggested by the International Science Council. It is an attempt to flip the science model towards transdisciplinarity.

The [core dilemma of urban health and wellbeing](#) is the same as the core dilemma of sustainability: improving health and wellbeing for all within planetary boundaries. It requires solutions and actions that are good enough for sustainability now. We should not expect silver bullets or panacea for solving the dilemma, but solutions which, after applying the best of our knowledge and doing the best we can, are good enough now and leave the doors open for improvements in future.

Science has a toolbox of well-established methods and procedures to deal with problems of complexity, and, by in large, interdisciplinarity has become the new normal in the science community. The main challenge which a science programme on urban health and wellbeing is now confronted with, is to become transdisciplinary, reaching out from the science domain to urban residents, policy- and decision makers, civil society organizations, stakeholders whose health and wellbeing is at risk by urban and environmental changes. Only by taking part in the knowledge co-creation process can the quality of decision-making be improved.

The difficulty of becoming transdisciplinary lies in the fact that science and politics need to engage with another, something Max Weber¹³⁹ had advised against. A science-policy partnership, however, seems necessary, given the complexity of the interconnected problems at hand. While being necessary, awareness must be created for the risks of such a partnership. It can lead to the extremes of politicized science and scientism; extremes which need to be avoided.

In order to escape that dilemma, the process of knowledge co-creation itself becomes a knowledge product on the way to solving complex problems. The knowledge required by the stakeholders who need to respond to changing environments (in and of cities and of the planet) is produced by themselves.¹⁴⁰ Creating such local [knowledge commons](#) for urban health and wellbeing can be regarded as the 'missing link' for translating global into local knowledge, action and policies.

For creating local [knowledge commons](#), the following systems knowledge is helpful: “An autopoietic system produces itself while simultaneously producing its own conditions, ... Systems thus always exist in an ‘environment’. The environment is not the ontic ‘real’ but rather is produced from within as the result of observing and reducing the complexity of its surroundings. Therefore the ‘environment’ of a system does not pre-exist the system but depends on its capacity for sensing and observing. The boundary between a system and its environment is ultimately decided by the system itself and is potentially open to change with each operation. Hence a system cannot interact directly with its environment and can only observe it via self-reference. Systems have “operational closure”, only operating with their own operative codes, programmes, and memory.”¹⁴¹

Apart from reconfirming Emmanuel Kant’s revolutionary way of thinking about reality, and Karl Popper’s views on the role of science and scientists - what does ‘creating local [knowledge commons](#)’ mean in the context of a systems science approach to urban health and wellbeing? By means of the (post-normal) systems science approach it provides stakeholder communities with the tools to produce their own knowledge and find solutions to problems which are specific to the geographical, cultural, ecological, technological, economic circumstances in which they live. How the planetary boundaries are scaled down and translated into local urban and community boundaries, is decided by the people who apply the data-knowledge-action system by means of which they engage in the co-creation of local knowledge. Communities need to be empowered and enabled to create their own knowledge commons in response to global challenges. Decentralized local knowledge commons are a necessary response to the Global Goals.

The modelling approach proposed here deviates from mathematical and technical modelling approaches. Knowledge is not outsourced to analysts, scientists or experts who are qualified to select and process data, build models, do the modelling, and then attempt to communicate the outcomes with decision-makers. The proposal made here is that communities of stakeholders are engaged in a knowledge creation process and thereby become the model themselves. It is a recoupling process in which people are reconnected to knowledge production and learning processes, re-integrated into measuring, modelling, and thereby empowered to managing their own lives and their urban environments.

Thereby, the knowledge production process is taken out of the ivory towers of academia and brought into the streets and to the urban communities, enabling them to co-create their own [knowledge commons](#), which they need to live the urban lives they want. Global goals like the New Urban Agenda and the Sustainable Development Goals can then persuasively be acted on locally.

The fragmented approach of producing global knowledge in science and (somehow) communicating it back to people and policy makers is replaced by a synthesis of knowledge and governance. According to the subsidiarity principle, knowledge is produced at the level and by those who are affected and have a stake. For that to happen it requires that new knowledge alliances for urban health and wellbeing are created and serious funding is made available. Such alliances can coincide with the idea of ‘science missions’ as recently proposed by the International Science Council.

This science and action plan will be accompanied by an implementation plan which will attempt to assess and measure the health condition of cities by means of an index. First deliberations on the construction of an index have been held with members of the scientific committee and will be executed in the second 10-year phase of the programme from 2025 onwards.

Glossary

Knowledge (or information) commons

The concept of the knowledge or information commons (used interchangeably) is inspired by the traditional commons, which are shared resources such as grazing land or fishing grounds. Just like these physical commons, knowledge commons are based on the idea that shared resources can benefit everyone. Knowledge and information commons are usually nonrivalrous (low subtractability), which means that the use of knowledge by some, does not reduce the use of the same knowledge by others, in fact it creates benefits for all the more it is used. And yet, the knowledge commons are vulnerable to social dilemmas, such as enclosure.

The digital age has led to ever more availability and access to knowledge and at the same time (and that is the dilemma) there are ever more restrictions to access, e.g., through property legislation, licensing, or overpricing. New technologies can enable the capture of once open public goods to most “global commons” such as the atmosphere, the biosphere or the deep seas. That ability fundamentally changes the nature of the resource, “with the resource being converted from a non-rivalrous, non-exclusionary public good into a common-pool resource that needs to be managed, monitored and protected to ensure sustainability and preservation.” (Hess and Ostrom 2004: 10)¹⁴².

Knowledge, although it seems ubiquitous, especially in digital form, “is in reality more vulnerable than ever before” (Hess and Ostrom 2004: 14). Collective action initiatives for the knowledge commons, such as open access and open-source software, ensure access. Knowledge commons are the institutionalized community governance of sharing and, creating a wide range of intellectual and cultural resources.

Co-creating knowledge commons for urban health and wellbeing, in the context of this global programme, means enabling and empowering local communities to make sense of global knowledge, e.g., about the planetary health status, the state of cities, or the state of global health and ecosystems; and respond to that knowledge at a local level by creating local knowledge commons for urban health and wellbeing, e.g., by deciding to use empty rooftops for solar energy or using public spaces for community gardens. Local knowledge commons are here presented as the ‘missing link’ for translating global knowledge into local action.

Empowering urban communities to create knowledge commons requires less command and control (regulation), and also not as much freedoms as possible (neither market nor state). It requires investments in social capital, self-governance, and collective action (Figure 26).

Figure 26: Local knowledge commons as missing link for transforming global knowledge into local action

Laws of thermodynamics

The first [law of thermodynamics](#) is about the conservation of energy. Energy can neither be created nor destroyed; it can only be transformed or transferred from one form to another. The law states that the total energy of an isolated system remains constant. The second law states that the sum of the entropies never decreases. Energy tends to change itself spontaneously into a more dispersed, random, or less organized, form. This is also referred to as an increase in entropy - entropy often being referred to as random, unavailable energy, or disorder. Living organisms and increasing complexity (in cities and other social systems) seem to contradict the 2nd law of thermodynamics, however, the amount of energy required to temporarily build up complexity and maintain low entropy in dissipative systems (like living organisms or cities), eventually results in higher total entropy levels over time.

Low entropy city

“A low-entropy city is defined as a responsive and conscious autopoietic human sociocultural niche that evolves and grows, enhancing its socio-ecological and structural complexity (reducing internal entropy) by adding and optimizing functional elements and synapses among those elements, while wastes (exported entropy to the biosphere) are minimized.” ([Pelorosso et al., 2017](#)).

Systemic dilemma of urban health and wellbeing

The dilemma refers to the fact that increasing health and wellbeing, or quality of life in cities, happens at the expense of resource depletion, ecosystem functioning or planetary health, and that declining planetary health has feeds back on urban health.

The dilemma arises due to the systemic nature of cities. They are complex social, ecological and technological urban systems nested into larger urban and ecological systems with which they exchange people, resources, energy, goods and services. When boundary conditions of the larger systems change in which cities are embedded, it will have consequences for urban systems and require them to adapt.

Data-Knowledge-Action systems (DAKAS)

Data-knowledge-action systems (for urban health and wellbeing) are systems which consolidate three components of a social learning and collective intelligence building process into one functional system. A DAKAS is process oriented and makes urban decision making less fragmented, better coordinated, more cost efficient, better informed, accountable, participatory and adaptive. It is a knowledge co-creation and deliberative governance process in one.

The process of a DAKAS consists of problem definition, system definition, data collection, data processing by collective knowledge creation, modelling and testing the models, decision-making, action and evaluation of the action impacts by renewed data collection and a renewed knowledge co-creation process.

Figure 27: The process of a Data-Knowledge-Action System

The structure of a DAKAS can resemble collective action arenas in which participants in action situations aim at solving problems. Multiple nested action arenas can exist at micro and macro scales from the family and neighborhood to the city and national level and consist of participants and action situations. Action situations are the social spaces where participants interact, exchange goods and services and solve problems.

Figure 28: The structure of a Data-Knowledge-Action system can resemble that of an action arena as proposed in the Institutional Analysis and Development framework proposed by Ostrom (2005)¹⁴³.

Mission-oriented science

The [ISC defines mission-oriented science](#) as “singularly goal-oriented and solutions-focused, science conducted for a limited period of time until a substantial challenge has been successfully addressed. Missions are of significant size, scope and ambition; and while focused on a clearly defined topic, question or goal, require interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary approaches: the input from a wide range of knowledge-holders and stakeholders, integration across disciplines and knowledge spheres, the development of applied as well as fundamental

knowledge and direct engagement with those who will enact policy and practical changes in response to the generated knowledge.”

Systems intelligence

Systems intelligence is intelligent behaviour in the context of complex systems involving interaction and feedback ([Saarinen and Hämäläinen 2004](#)).

Science-based governance for urban health and wellbeing

Science-based governance happens, when the collective process of knowledge generation for urban health and wellbeing becomes integral part of the governance of urban health and wellbeing. It is about constantly adjusting governance procedures according to new knowledge generated. Data-Knowledge-Action systems are the mechanism enabling science-based governance.

Post-normal science

A scientific inquiry and problem-solving framework proposed by [Silvio Funtowicz and Jerome Ravetz](#) applied to problems of complexity. The approach recognizes uncertainty, value loadings and plural legitimate perspectives as integral elements of scientific inquiry, particularly in the cases where facts are uncertain, values are in dispute, stakes are high and decisions are urgent. In those cases a strategy based on ‘extended peer review’ is advocated. When scientists are not dealing with uncertainties but calculable risks, an expert-based approach and traditional problem-solving strategies, such as applied science or professional consultancy, could be more effective. While ‘normal’ science approaches are still necessary, when dealing with problems of complexity, they are not sufficient. The post-normal science approach provides a framework for an extended participation in decision-making. The quality of decisions and policies made relies on continuous dialogues and deliberations between all those affected.

The post-normal science approach is thereby not only restricted to the traditional domain of science, as for example express in [logical positivism](#), it extends to the domain of decision-making, governance and thereby to policy domain. The strict divide between knowledge production by science and its diffusion into society is overcome and merged. [Data-Knowledge-Action](#) systems are a methodological materialization of the post-normal science approach.

Living organism

Zhao et al. (2024)¹⁴⁴ argue, that *“From the Charter of Athens to the Charter of Machu Picchu to the 2030 New Urban Agenda, the image of the city as a “machine” has been gradually replaced by that of an “organism”. However, the urban governance mentality of treating cities as “machines” has not been genuinely transformed and is still firmly rooted in past regimes of urban governance and development (Batty, 2012)¹⁴⁵”* The authors provide references that would justify perceiving cities as living organisms, as they exhibit metabolism, self-organisation, adaptivity, self-similar hierarchy, and can be considered “ill” when diseases spread, pollution, urban sprawl, congestion, pollution and housing shortages occur.

Logical positivism

A movement in science, prominently advanced by the Vienna Circle, arguing that science should take an inductive approach and observe or logically explain phenomena to understand them and apply verification to prove them. It assumes that the world works according to general laws which need to be discovered. Karl Popper criticized logical positivism among others due to its assumption of the scientific method being value-free. Value judgements are part of the scientific inquiry, not only because all experimental designs are made on particular assumptions and biases, but also because decisions cannot be made if value judgements are not made to decide when sufficient knowledge has been acquired.

McLaren (2019)¹⁴⁶ sees a connection between the logical positivists' view that indubitable knowledge can be achieved through the sheer quantity of data accumulated, thereby reducing uncertainties and making questioning unnecessary, and the attempts to create society 5.0. Promises of certainty, however, create an obsession with safety and security "which is generating a disproportionate culture of fear leaving us more and more vulnerable to and impacted by, uncertainties."¹⁴⁷

Ecological civilization

Ecological Civilization is a response to the extent of ecological destruction which is undermining the conditions for life. The idea of ecological civilisation aims at the health of living systems, instead of merely creating and accumulating wealth. It shares many visions of urban futures with the idea of 'Society 5.0' except that it tends to reject hedonism, utilitarianism, liberalism and capitalism, and instead focuses on collective action, commoning, and various aspects of socialism. Gare^{148,149} and Lent¹⁵⁰ see ecological civilization in cities, as cities with community gardens, urban commons, and essential services accessible and reachable within a 20-minute walk and cars banned from city centers. The process philosopher McLaren (2019)¹⁵¹ criticizes health achievements on the basis of ever more energy consumption as unsustainable and calls for holistic approaches to health under ecological civilisation, which create the conditions for self-healing of people but also of the relationship between people and nature. Reaffirming earlier thoughts of Herman Daly and John Cobb¹⁵², he calls for an understanding of 'the whole' and reconnecting to communities.

Society 5.0

Society 5.0¹⁵³ was proposed in Japan's 5th [Science and Technology Basic Plan](#) as a future society that Japan should aspire to. It follows the hunting society (Society 1.0), agricultural society (Society 2.0), industrial society (Society 3.0), and information society (Society 4.0). According to the [government of Japan Society 5.0](#) will be realized by "...connecting and sharing medical data that is now dispersed in various hospitals, effective medical treatment based on data would be provided. Remote medical care makes it possible that elderly people will no longer have to visit hospitals frequently. Also, you can measure and manage health data such as heart rate while at home, so that it will be possible to extend people's healthy life expectancy."

Urban health

Definition: The health of cities as complex social, ecological and technological systems and the planetary health condition on which it depends.

Health and wellbeing of people living in cities is one component of urban health. The other is the healthy functioning of urban systems within their environments, the conditions which constitute planetary health.

Definitions of terms are normative as they determine the focus and perspective taken when using the term. In this case the normative standpoint has been shaped over the first ten years of the UHWB programme and it aims to equally balance the 'health' focus of urban health, which views people's health as the unit of analysis and urban health as the 'health of people in cities', with the 'urban' focus, which views the city as complex system in a particular condition or state, which can be healthy or unhealthy for people and the planet. Like the human is the focus of analysis in 'human health', the city is the focus of analysis in 'urban health'.

Putting equal importance to 'health' and 'urban' in the definition of 'urban health' connects the term 'urban health' closer with the concept of [ecosystems health](#).

That shift in focus promises to better solve the dilemma of sustainable development, which is that the improvement of human health and wellbeing is based on the ecological goods and resources of the planet which are being depleted and their functions are being compromised in the process of improving human health and wellbeing.

Cities

Complex social, ecological and technological (living) systems with higher population densities than in rural areas, administratively demarcated but geographically interconnected with other city systems and regions. Their scaling properties and metabolism differ from biological systems, or companies.

Ecosystem health

Ecosystem health can be defined as the state or condition of an ecosystem in which its dynamic attributes are expressed within the normal ranges of activity, or as the state or condition of an ecosystem that is capable of sustaining ecosystem functioning. Ecosystem health is a normative concept that implies specific societal goals. The normative terms are mostly institutionalized in national and international policy and law^{154, 155, 156, 157, 158, 159}.

Planetary health

The health of human civilisation and the state of the natural systems on which it depends.¹⁶⁰

Politics of uncertainty

A [politics of uncertainty](#) questions attempts to frame uncertainty as calculable risks. Urban health and wellbeing challenges are often complex and interconnected and therefore need to adopt strategies that do not attempt to abolish uncertainties by more data-heavy models. It also changes some ideas of progress where some are winners and others losers of a linear development process. Alternatively, circular processes of growth, renewal and learning, are considered.¹⁶¹ Responding to uncertainties with a politics of uncertainty requires less efforts in controlling and more efforts in collective, mutualistic and convivial types of governance which emphasize responsibility and care.

Co-benefits of urban health

Co-benefits of urban health are positive, additional effects created from implementing health or other policies in cities. These benefits often extend beyond immediate health outcomes for people creating a ripple effect of positive change in urban and peri-urban environments, thereby, e.g., leading to the sustainable development goals. Co-benefits of actions or policies are benefits from interventions with synergy effects or [synergistic satisfiers](#) of human needs.

Human-scale urban development

Human scale urban development ensures that the urban environment with which urban residents interact every day is of a size and shape to use and feel comfortable and contributes to their health and wellbeing. It also refers to how people perceive their urban environment and how their environment shapes and influences their lives. Human-scale development also refers to community development, self-reliance, and global processes that are implemented at a local level, participatory planning and collaboration between state and civil society (see ref. [Gehl, 2010](#) and [Max-Neef, 1991](#)).

Urban areas

According to the European Commission's (EC) definition human settlements consist of:

- **Urban center:** must have a minimum of 50,000 inhabitants **plus** a population density of at least 1500 people per square kilometre (km²) or density of build-up area greater than 50%.
- **Urban cluster:** must have a minimum of 5,000 inhabitants **plus** a population density of at least 300 people per square kilometre (km²).
- **Rural:** fewer than 5,000 inhabitants.

The EC reports that 52% of the world's population lived in urban centers, 33% in urban clusters, and 15% in rural areas in 2015, which means 85% (more than 6.1 billion people) of the global population lived in urban areas in 2015.

Intelligence (Human)

Landgrebe and Smith (2023) define human intelligence as a combination of primal and objectifying intelligence. Primal intelligence is a precondition for learning and is 'the (adaptive) power of making a meaningful response in the face of a new situation' (Scheler 1961)¹⁶². Objectifying intelligence is the ability to not just adapt to environments but also actively change environments and make them fit to what the intelligent actors have in their minds. That kind of intelligence involves conscious intentionality (Searle 1975)¹⁶³.

Accordingly, (author's interpretation) human intelligence is the ability of an individual or group to spontaneously find a sensible / meaningful solution to a novel (problem-)situation without having been prepared or trained for it, including the act of intentionally changing the environment so as to facilitate that problem solving capability.¹⁶⁴

Collective intelligence

"Collective intelligence has been defined as "...groups of individuals doing things collectively that seem intelligent" (Malone 2006)¹⁶⁵. Google and Wikipedia are examples. The State of the Future 2010 report defines collective intelligence as "an emergent property from synergies among data/information/knowledge, and experts (...) that continually learns from feedback

to produce (...) knowledge for better decisions than these elements acting alone.” Atlee (2006)¹⁶⁶ distinguishes collective intelligence from co-intelligence which “...embraces more than collective intelligence (CI), the intelligence of groups. It includes at least multi-modal intelligence, collaborative intelligence, resonant intelligence, uni- versal intelligence, and wisdom (see <http://tinyurl.com/2l28nh>, Accessed March 10, 2024). By itself—and especially without wisdom (embracing the big picture)—collective intelligence, like individual intelligence, can be used in harmful ways, such as building gas chambers and new technologies with disastrous “side effects.” Citizen juries, assemblies, consensus conferences, participatory decision making, citizen deliberative councils, ... are actually methods for manifesting consciousness at higher scales of social organization by cognitive synergies. Those are evolutionary processes of conscious building. The scales range from individual, to family, group, organization, city, state, global intelligence. In different forms of collective intelligence, group intelligence can be more powerful than individual intelligence by seeing a bigger, more complete picture and overcoming blind spots—very much depending on how the collective process itself is designed.” (Gatzweiler et al. 2017)¹⁶⁷

Complex system

“A system characterized by dependence on an arbitrary combination of element types, different interaction types between elements, force overlay (several forces acting at the same time and thereby potentially interacting), phase spaces which cannot be predicted from the system elements, and by non-ergodicity, drivenness, evolutionary properties, and non-fixable boundary conditions.” ([Landgrebe and Smith 2023](#))

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